

UNIVERSITY OF LAUSANNE

MASTER'S THESIS

The impact of climate commitment on corporate performance

Author:

Alexandre GIMMI

Department of Finance

Faculty of Business and Economics

University of Lausanne

Supervisor:

Prof. Guido PALAZZO

Department of Strategy, Globalization and Society

Faculty of Business and Economics

University of Lausanne

Expert:

Luis SOUSA GOMES

Department of Strategy, Globalization and Society

Faculty of Business and Economics

University of Lausanne

Master of Science in Finance (MScF)
Faculty of Business and Economics (HEC)

August 25th, 2020

Abstract. As a result of the general awareness of the gravity of climate change, research on the link between corporate performance and climate commitment is increasing and subject to particular attention. On the one side, numerous academic works focus on the relationship between corporate financial and environmental performance, without acknowledging the important limitations of such causality. On the other side, some studies introduce new economic models without explaining the reasons for changing the current models. This paper takes into account the obstacles faced by companies with regards to their climate commitment. Indeed, this paper criticizes the current definition of corporate responsibility and performance and presents alternative models that could allow society to face the climate crisis. This thesis explains that companies must assume political responsibilities, and that their performance must be defined by their capacity to maximize their economic, natural and social capital.

Abstract. Ayant grandi avec la prise de conscience générale sur la sérieux du changement climatique, la recherche académique sur les liens entre la performance et l'engagement climatique jouit d'une attention particulière. D'une part, de nombreux travaux académiques se concentrent sur la relation entre performance financière et environnementale, sans souligner les importantes limites d'une telle causalité. D'autre part, certaines études apportent de nouveaux modèles économiques sans expliquer les raisons de changer les modèles actuels. Ce papier prend en compte les obstacles que rencontre l'engagement climatique des entreprises, à savoir, la définition actuelle de responsabilité et de performance des entreprises et propose des solutions alternatives pour que la société puisse faire face à l'ampleur de la crise climatique. Ce papier explique que les entreprises doivent assumer des responsabilités politiques, et que leur performance doit être définie par leur capacité à maximiser leur capital économique, naturel et social.

Keywords: Finance; Environment; Social; Performance; Global Warming.

JEL Classification: Q540; M140.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	5
1.1	RESEARCH QUESTION	5
1.2	CONTEXT.....	6
1.3	EXPECTATIONS FOR THE FUTURE	9
1.4	ADAPTATION VERSUS MITIGATION	11
1.5	THE ROLE OF COMPANIES	12
2	FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE	14
2.1	IMPACT ON COMPANIES	14
2.2	OBSTACLES OF CHANGES.....	15
2.3	FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND CLIMATE COMMITMENT	17
2.3.1	<i>Previous findings</i>	17
2.3.2	<i>Recent developments</i>	18
2.3.3	<i>Financial performance and mitigation</i>	20
2.3.4	<i>Financial performance and adaptation</i>	21
2.3.5	<i>Corporate performance</i>	22
2.4	FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND CLIMATE NON-COMMITMENT.....	22
2.4.1	<i>Financial performance and legal risk</i>	23
2.4.2	<i>Financial performance and divestment risk</i>	25
2.4.3	<i>Financial performance and climate-related risks</i>	27
2.5	CONCLUSION ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE.....	27
3	PERFORMANCE AND RESPONSIBILITY	29
3.1	INEQUALITIES	29
3.2	CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY	30
3.3	THE CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITY	32
3.3.1	<i>The blurring limit between the economy and politics</i>	32
3.3.2	<i>Political corporate social responsibility</i>	34
3.3.3	<i>Political corporate social responsibility and climate change</i>	35
3.4	THE CORPORATE PERFORMANCE	36
3.4.1	<i>Corporate governance</i>	36
3.4.2	<i>The sustainable value-added metric</i>	37
3.4.3	<i>Leadership</i>	39
3.5	CONCLUSION ON CLIMATE CHANGE.....	40
4	CONCLUSION	42
	REFERENCES	44

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CH₄	Methane
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
CSR	Corporate social responsibility
EVA	Economic value added
GCP	Global carbon project
GHG	Greenhouse gases
GRI	Global reporting initiative
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
NGOs	Non-governmental organizations
O₃	Ozone
SRI	Sustainable and responsible investments
SVA	Sustainable value added
TCFD	Task force on climate-related financial disclosures
UNFCC	United nations framework convention on climate change

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research question

Most studies on the relation between environmental and financial performances are based on a financial definition of corporate performance. Therefore, the results are usually limited due to the complexity of maintaining environmental and financial objectives at the same time. Other research, which focused exclusively on environmental sustainability expresses alternative models of society without indicating the reasons for this change or the limitation of the actual economic models. Consequently, this paper aims to highlight the major obstacles for companies to commit to climate change in the current economic models and to pave the way for a new definition of corporate responsibility and performance to permit a better response to the actual climate crisis.

The first section of this paper introduces the phenomenon of climate change; its past, present and future states as well as the actual and forthcoming impacts occurred on biodiversity and society are enumerated. In addition, the limitations of considering the possibility to solve climate change and the necessity for humanity to anticipate these changes are discussed. Finally, the companies' legitimate and essential mobilization to enable an efficient global response to climate change is highlighted.

The second section of this thesis shows that perceiving financial performance as the primary indicator of corporate performance fails to account for the welfare of companies given the climate crisis. The discussion is based on a systematic analysis of financial incentives for companies to engage in mitigation or adaptation measures from two distinct situations. The first situation is incentives for companies to commit to climate change on a voluntary and private basis. The second situation is an analysis of climate-related risks that could force companies to engage in mitigation or adaptation measures due to the adverse effects on their market value if these risks were not anticipated sufficiently.

The third section of this thesis shows that the definition of corporate performance and responsibility must include social, environmental and economic perspectives. The discussion

is based on the dynamics of a globalized world affected by climate change and argues that companies already endorse political responsibilities. This section develops an analysis based on the concept of political corporate social responsibility, a field of study that could be an efficient response to climate change. In addition, a new metric of corporate performance is developed and the role of business leaders in the global answer to global warming is emphasized. To conclude, the different findings, their implication for practitioners and the limitations of this paper are discussed.

1.2 Context

In recent times, climate change has taken center stage of political debates in many developed countries and has become a worldwide societal issue. Even though various perceptions exist regarding the exact causes and consequences of this complex phenomenon, global warming is no longer questioned in the scientific literature (Cook et al., 2013). Anthropogenic emissions being the main contributor to climate change is unequivocally accepted (IPCC, 2013). However, declaring that climate change is a topical issue is a euphemism since it has been the object of international debates and negotiations for decades.

Greenhouse gases (GHG), in particular carbon dioxide (CO₂), ozone (O₃) and methane (CH₄), are the main responsible for global warming. They thicken the naturally existing gas layer on the planet and make it more difficult for the heat to evade in the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases concentrations were first measured in the late 1950s at the observatory of Mauna Loa in Hawaii. This is where the first evidence of a growing increase in CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere correlated with the combustion of fossil fuels was documented (Keeling, 1960). Therefore, anthropogenic emissions were already positioned at the center of the climate issue over half a century ago.

The scientific community's awareness regarding the potential threat of global warming rose in the end of the 1970s. This resulted in the first world conference on climate in 1979, where the greenhouse effect and global warming were discussed and debated internationally for the first time. Almost a decade later, in 1988, an international response was implemented with the creation of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), which comprises hundreds of climate scientists across several specialties and disciplines. The IPCC's first assessment

report (1990) served as a basis for the framework convention of Rio de Janeiro in 1992, where the stabilization of GHG was at stake to promote a sustainable planet for future generations. The IPCC's second report in 1995 and the signature of the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 intensified the media coverage of climate change, which consequently increased the public awareness of global warming (Boykoff & Roberts, 2008).

The Kyoto Protocol could have led to a decisive acceleration of international action for climate change as, for the first time, quantifiable and constraining objectives were set for the signatories. Nevertheless, the Kyoto Protocol was criticised due to its non-binding nature, and since the withdrawal of the United States in 2001, has almost been abandoned (Boehmer-Christiansen & Kellow, 2003). The European Union consolidated its role as a leader in the climate change fight (Zito, 2005), adopting the energy-climate package in 2008 and actualizing it in 2014 with the ambitious goal to reduce the EU's GHG emissions by at least 40% by 2030.

In 2015, world leaders overcame their differences and founded the Paris Agreement. Its hybrid nature allowed each country to determine its contribution, with a reinforcement of their pledges every five years. Envisioning the future, the next crucial international conference on climate change will take place in November 2021 in Glasgow, where the 197 countries that have ratified the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) will gather for the 26th conference of the parties (COP26). This will be a decisive meeting since the subsequent reinforcement of national pledges is not planned before 2026, a gravely distant date if the world wants to mitigate the dynamics of climate change.

Despite these numerous international gatherings that started decades ago, there are major concerns regarding the inconsistency of countries' actions to fight climate change (Robiou du Pont and Meinshausen, 2018; Watson et al., 2019). A simple look at the anthropogenic emissions of GHG, increasing by 2.2% per year between 2000-2010 compared to an average rhythm of 1.3% from 1970-2000 (IPCC, 2014) demonstrates that international commitments were inadequate. According to the climatologists from the Global Carbon Project (GCP), in 2018, the global fossil fuel emissions of CO₂ increased by 2.1% to a record atmospheric concentration of 407.8 particles per million, higher than at any point in at least the past 800,000 years (Friedlingstein et al., 2019, Lenton et al., 2019). Similarly, energy consumption rose by 2.3% in 2018, nearly twice the average rate of growth since 2010 (IEA, 2019). Thus, as of this date, countries' engagement has been insufficient to reduce global GHG emissions. The

question is to know whether the state of the climate in 2020 can attest of this international passivity.

Today, temperatures are slightly over 1° C above preindustrial levels, with regional variations uniformly geographically distributed (Pithan & Mauritsen, 2014). The extreme warm temperature anomalies observed in the Arctic have catastrophic consequences for the Greenland ice sheet, which is melting at an accelerating pace (Overland et al., 2019). Although sea levels have remained stable since the last deglaciation 3,000 years ago (Lambeck et al., 2010), the global mean sea level started to rise again during the 20th century and at a faster pace in recent years (Dangendorf et al., 2017). Moreover, the frequency and severity of extreme weather events such as hurricanes, droughts and wildfires have increased over the past decade (Walsh et al., 2019; Radeloff et al., 2018; Harvey, 2019) and climate change has reduced crop yields by 1-2% per decade over the past century (Wiebe et al., 2015).

The impacts of climate change are also observable within the oceans. Approximately half of the coral reef on the planet has died over the last 30 years, mainly due to the rise in temperature and the acidification of the oceans (Sosdian et al., 2018; Cheal et al., 2017). Similarly, climate change has severe repercussions on life forms on lands. A decrease of the total biomass of wildlife and plants of 80% and 50% respectively (Bar-On et al., 2018) as well as a rapid decline of 50% of insect species have been observed (Sánchez-Bayo & Wyckhuys, 2019). In fact, the extinction rate is ten to hundreds of times higher than average over millions of years (IPBES, 2019). These statistics confirm that climate change has triggered the sixth major extinction event (Thomas et al., 2004) and since the five warmest years in the 1880-2019 record all have occurred in the 2015-2019 period (NOAA, 2019), there is no break in sight.

Yet, the welfare of the humankind strongly depends upon the health of the planet. Scientists estimate that terrestrial and marine diversity together sequester 5.6 gigatons of carbon per year and that oceans generate nearly half of the oxygen in the atmosphere (Gjerde et al., 2016). Only a living ocean with a stable ecosystem can assume its role of carbon sink. Moreover, many coastal economies rely upon ocean and marine life, while insect pollination's, required for 75% of the world's food crops, is worth approximately 10% of the total value of the food supply (Bartomeus et al., 2014; Pecl et al., 2017; Spalding et al., 2014; Dirzo et al., 2014). In view of the above observations, it is clear that by controlling and shaping the world in the past, humanity

has generated major perturbations in today's ecological system. Thus, one should question how climate change will materialize in the future.

1.3 Expectations for the future

Precise predictions of the evolution of climate change are nearly impossible to perform. In fact, the complexity of climate change does not come from the specific way variables of the climate system behave individually but from the interactions between these variables (Goldenfeld & Kadanoff, 1999). This explains why scientific opinion diverges with regards to the evolution of global warming. Nevertheless, climate experts' long-term simulations indicate that in a business-as-usual scenario, temperatures in the 21st century should increase from 2.6° C to 4.8° C above preindustrial levels (Collins & Knutti, 2013). Although these forecasts are still debated, a consensus among climate experts, which is also the landmark of the Paris Agreement, states that humanity must “hold the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2° C above preindustrial levels and pursue efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5° C” (UNFCCC, 2015, p3).

The IPCC Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5° C (2018) estimated that to have a 66% chance to stay below 1.5° C, global GHG emissions must not exceed 420 gigatons of CO₂ equivalent. This corresponds to a decade of the 2018's global emission level. In other words, to target the 1.5° C' threshold, global GHG emissions must be lowered by 7.6% per year on average starting from 2020, with a greater percentage if that action is delayed (UNEP, 2019). Furthermore, the norms of scientific reporting and analysis can be questioned. Studies have observed that climate experts often minimized climate effects by “erring on the side of the least drama” to avoid public rejection (Brysse et al, 2013). The IPCC's calculations generally assume a quasi-linear relationship between cumulative CO₂ emissions and global warming. However, the upward trend of recent data is more consistent with a non-linear modification of the environment (Malmquist, 2018; Wadhams, 2018).

The insufficient international commitments and the fact that climate experts forecast the carbon budget to be exhausted in a decade (a projection that may be underestimated to avoid public rejection or completely inaccurate in the case of non-linear changes), imply that targeting a

global temperature increase of 1.5° C is optimistic. One should question the expected consequences of reaching the 2° C' threshold.

At this point, it is necessary to introduce the idea of a tipping point, that is, an abrupt change that results in an irreversible momentum. Some climate experts warned that such a planetary threshold could be activated with a global temperature rise as low as 2° C above the preindustrial epoch (Lenton et al., 2008; Steffen et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2015; Wadhams, 2018). Due to the negative synergies between deforestation, climate change and the use of fire to clear lands for crops, a tipping point could be triggered by 20-25% of the Amazon forest cover being lost (Lovejoy & Nobre, 2018). Besides forests, and based on the current pace of global warming, scientists believe that the ice-free Arctic may become a reality at the end of the summer melt season within the next decade (Wadhams, 2016). This situation could cause a perturbation of the Atlantic meridional ocean circulation, which consequently could accelerate ice melting in the East Antarctic ice-sheet (Mengel & Levermann, 2014). As a result, an ice-free Arctic is expected to increase the global temperature by a substantial degree (Bendell, 2018). Although uncertain, these scenarios of unstoppable dynamics demonstrate that even low temperature rise can trigger catastrophic events.

Besides tipping points, reaching a 2°C global warming has several reasons to be considered unsafe (Schleussner et al., 2017). Such a temperature rise would have staggering impacts on economies, societies and biodiversity including the disappearance of entire ecosystems. In fact, 99% of coral reefs are projected to be lost (Frieler et al., 2018) and the combination of the loss of corals and the rise in ocean acidification are expected to reduce fisheries' productivity by half (Rogers et al, 2017). The total species loss for insects, plants and vertebrates is projected to reach 27%, 30% and 10% respectively (Warren et al., 2018). In addition, a meta-analysis of crop yield simulations found that the aggregate production for wheat, rice and maize will significantly decrease as a result of a 2°C global warming (Challinor et al., 2014). For example, in China, the decrease in the yields of wheat, corn and rice are expected to amount 18%, 45% and 36% respectively (Zhang et al., 2016).

Moreover, neither technology nor science are sufficient responses to the climate challenge. The requested time to implement new technologies at a global scale will probably be insufficient to reduce the quantity of heating already locked into the atmosphere (Bendell, 2018). Moreover, the ecological benefits of technological advances have been systematically reversed by the

rebound effect (Ruzzenenti et al., 2019). This effect is the reduction in expected gains from new technologies that increase the efficiency of resource use, due to a rise of consumption of that resource. Geoengineering¹ cannot be considered as an appropriate solution neither. Given the complexity of climate change, proposals are “largely speculative and unproven, and with the risk of unknown side-effects” (IPCC, 2007, p15). Natural climate solutions² may also be inefficient since the rise of environmental destruction due to extreme meteoritical events may reverse their positive benefits (Marshall, 2020). Lastly, relying upon a global greening effect³ is a risky speculation (Keenan et al, 2016; Penuelas et al., 2017). Therefore, there is no silver bullet to climate change.

Finally, even if the most ambitious targets of the Paris Agreement were successfully reached, experts suppose that climate change will continue for the foreseeable future in any case (Köhler et al., 2018; Berlemann & Steinhardt, 2017). This trend can be explained by the residence time⁴, which ranges from 5 to 15 years (Cawley, 2011) and the adjustment time⁵, which is expected to exceed a century (Joos et al., 2013; Lord et al., 2016). Put differently, even if the whole world ceases emitting GHG today, the heating and instability already locked into the atmosphere will continue to damage biodiversity for at least several years (residence time), if not centuries (adjustment time).

In conclusion, humankind must face the evidence that evading from the consequences of climate change in the coming decades is not feasible. Individuals should not be duped by the blind spot of any culture, that is, the inability to conceive its own possible extinction (Lear, 2009). Humanity has to adapt to climate change.

1.4 Adaptation versus mitigation

There exist two strategies for addressing global warming. Adaptation measures are the actions taken to reduce direct exposures to climate change for the coming decades, and mitigation

¹ The manipulation of an environmental process in an attempt to reduce climate change.

² Restoring forests and other ecosystems to give back the earth its autonomy.

³ Relying on the fact that vegetated lands expands due to rising levels of atmospheric CO₂ in the atmosphere.

⁴ The average amount of time a CO₂ molecule remains in air before it is absorbed.

⁵ The atmospheric lifetime of a CO₂ molecule before it is removed from the atmosphere

measures are the actions taken to lower greenhouse gases emissions in order to reduce the intensity and severity of climate change in future decades. Although adapting to the present impacts of climate change and mitigating its future consequences are two complementary and synergistic strategies (Tol, 2005), the concept of adaptation took time to emerge in international discussions. The main reason has been the fear that international commitments to adaptation measures would be made at the expense of mitigation measures (Khan & Roberts, 2013).

However, the insufficient international actions to stay below a 2° C global temperature rise and the observations of a more intense and severe climate change have raised critics concerning the exclusive international focus on mitigation (Berrang-Ford et al., 2019). The concept of simultaneously employing both measures has been adopted at the Paris Agreement in 2015, where climate experts have admitted that an efficient global response to climate change must include a fair balance between adaptation and mitigation measures. Nonetheless, there is still a strong imbalance between the two methods in practice. For example, of the USD 70 billion pledge in 2017 from industrialised countries to finance the most vulnerable nations to climate change, the share going to adaptation and mitigation measures accounted for 19% and 81% respectively (OECD, 2019).

Global warming calls for actions to increase today's societal resilience while reducing tomorrow's impact of climate change. However, for the moment, states' commitments have been insufficient. In fact, states' actions rarely go beyond their borders since they principally focus on the welfare of their own citizens. Therefore, states do not appear to be the optimal candidates to respond to the global issue of climate change.

1.5 The role of companies

Companies are present all around the globe and are the intermediaries between individuals' needs and consumption. This combination puts them on center stage to support the risks and consequences of climate change. Each economic agent will be affected by climate change either directly through the disruption of their business operations and damages on their infrastructures or indirectly through the vulnerability of their suppliers and clients (Agrawala et al., 2011). Therefore, climate change is a serious threat that companies must anticipate.

Previous chapters have shown that climate change has local, national, and international dimensions. Thus, companies' local market knowledge in addition to their worldwide presence are advantages that make them powerful candidates to respond to this issue. Moreover, as intermediaries between needs and consumption, companies are at the center of the quasi-totality of global GHG emissions. By assuming responsibility of climate change, companies have the power to seriously influence this issue. Therefore, companies' repercussions on the global response to climate change can be far greater than those of any actions by states, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or citizens. Finally, the economic opportunities and costs of climate change, such as the increasing demand for environmentally friendly products or the growing number of environmental regulations are also powerful drivers that should incite companies to engage in adaptation or mitigation measures.

In this light, companies are legitimate and essential stakeholders to mobilise in the global response to climate change. This explains why this paper is orientated toward companies. The choice not to focus on other entities such as individuals or NGOs does not imply that their role in the fight against climate change is not important. This restrictive choice is dictated by the constraints of a thesis.

2 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

2.1 Impact on companies

The Stern review on the economics of climate change, a report published by a former World Bank chief economist (Stern, 2006), indicated that one of the main consequences of climate change is that it will impoverish the world. A vulnerability index reported that 67 countries, accounting for over 20% of the world GDP in 2020, have been listed as highly to extremely exposed to climate change (Verisk Maplecroft, 2013). Moreover, the aggregated damage of future floods on assets due to climate change in coastal cities are estimated to amount to USD 60-63 billion per year by 2050, compared to a current yearly cost of USD 6 billion (Hallegatte et al., 2013). Additionally, heat stress is expected to decrease average working hours by 2.2% by 2030, principally in lower-middle- and low-income countries, which is equivalent to a yearly loss of USD 2.4 trillion (Kjellstrom et al., 2019). In fact, in each considered scenario of climate change, the expected worldwide economic losses are substantial (Calzadilla et al., 2013).

Some essential industries will face tremendous challenges. Although 33% of the oil, 50% of the natural gases and 80% of the coal global reserves must remain in the ground to prevent a 2° C global temperature rise (McGlade & Ekins, 2015), the energy industry has the responsibility to meet a 50% expected rise of global energy consumption by 2050 (EIA, 2019). The same observation may be drawn for the food industry. By 2050, the number of people to feed is expected to increase by 25% (UN, 2019), while climate change reduces crop yields and lands (Challinor et al., 2014). In addition, the insurance industry is extremely vulnerable to climate change. Not only insurers have to pay for the physical costs occurred to the goods they insure, but are also exposed through their investments in financial assets and real estate. To mitigate these risks, insurers shift the costs to their customers (Dahlen & Peter, 2012), which results in higher payments and risks premiums for insurance coverage for businesses.

Climate change affects a firm's environment, and the environment in which a firm is embedded influences its performance and market value (Werther & Chandler, 2005). Therefore, each company is exposed to climate change through their insurances price, resources, infrastructures, suppliers and customers (Agrawala et al., 2011). An analysis of the financial impacts of climate

change on 225 of the world's largest companies found that a total of USD 1 trillion of assets are at risk and that these damages are likely to materialize before 2024 (CDP, 2019).

In addition, researchers have concluded that the cost of inaction to climate change is superior to the cost of adaptation (Ackerman et al., 2008; De Bruin et al., 2009; WEF 2020). In a scenario of a strong global adaptation to climate change, the investment costs would reach approximately 1% of the world GDP. Alternatively, in the case of inaction, the costs are expected to have a magnitude ten times greater (Stern, 2006). Avoiding losses is not the only motivation to anticipate these changes. There are economic opportunities to adapt to climate change (UNGC, 2011; UNEP, 2012). For example, The Global Commission on Adaptation (GCA, 2019) stated that return on investments to climate-proof businesses in 2020 could reach 400% by 2030.

In essence, each economic agent will be directly or indirectly impacted by climate change. The costs of inaction are greater than the costs of action and there are economic incentives to adapt. Therefore, business leaders should not perceive climate change as an environmental issue but more as a market transition (Hoffman & Woody, 2008). This means that companies should have already anticipated climate change. However, only a minority of firms are quantifying climate-related risks in their operations and those who do are presumably underestimating them substantially (Goldstein et al., 2019).

2.2 Obstacles of changes

The veracity of climate change and its negative consequences on the welfare of the society are globally acknowledged (Stokes and al., 2015). At the same time, individuals, companies, and states do not act sufficiently to reduce the future impacts of climate change. One should question how an entity can tolerate a threatening reality and not change its behavior.

Individuals tend to focus on the risks they consider to be the most important to them at a certain point in time (Adger et al., 2007). However, climate change is not a one-time event; rather, it is a continual process with multiple perceptions of causality, timing and damages. The long-term dynamics of climate change and the difficulty to perceive or experience its consequences inhibit it from becoming a priority for a majority of individuals (Lorenzoni & Pidgeon, 2006).

Piaget (2005) introduced the concept of equilibration, which is the combination of two fundamental tendencies of every cognitive system: the assimilation and the accommodation of information. For an individual, it is complicated to mobilize his cognitive structures to accommodate to a distant, slow and abstract modification of its environment. Therefore, climate change makes people vulnerable to their instinctive habit to confirm their preexisting assumption of reality by reshaping new information. This unbalanced learning about the climate creates internal tension and results in a confirmation bias. Therefore, responses to climate change have been limited by human cognition (Grothmann & Patt, 2005; Moser, 2005).

At a company level, questioning a firm's mission and priorities is demanding and time consuming, especially for business leaders already pressured by other responsibilities. Yet, the core of a company has always been to adapt to a perpetually evolving environment. Therefore, expecting managers to give climate change a special attention is a legitimate assumption. However, in the eyes of the business leaders surveyed by the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2019), none of the world's ten greatest business risks were related to environmental concerns. This finding highlights the first obstacle for companies: climate change is a blind spot for business leaders.

The power of free markets, property rights and market efficiency have inculcated generations of managers that by promoting their company's interests, they promoted the interests of the society. A tenet of financial management is that a corporation's primary aim is to increase its shareholders' wealth by maximizing the income from its activities (Friedman, 1970). Thus, the next obstacle is what Mark Carney (2015) defines as the tragedy of horizons: managers are framed on short-term profit maximization when climate change has a long-term horizon.

These personal, cognitive and institutional obstacles are deeply ingrained in the values and norms of business leaders. In fact, it has been observed that people with a higher degree of academic education tend to support more firmly the existing economic and social systems than those with less education (Schmidt, 2000). Therefore, proving that climate commitment is financially rewarded by the market could be imperative to include climate change in companies' practices.

2.3 Financial performance and climate commitment

Evidence of a significantly positive relationship between climate engagement and corporate financial performance could persuade business leaders to commit to climate change on a private and voluntary basis. Climate proponents claim that the reduction of costs from the decreased use of resources or the improvement of brand perception are beneficial for companies (Kolk & Pinske, 2007), while skepticism persists in light of the important direct expenses of climate commitment and the uncertainty of their long-term returns (Hart & Ahuja, 1996). Therefore, a review of the previous findings is necessary to assess whether a firm can increase its financial performance by enhancing its environmental performance.

2.3.1 Previous findings

In a literature review that exclusively focused on the relationship between corporate environmental and financial performance, Hjort (2016) found that empirical evidence is mixed. Arguments have been made on both sides as to whether climate commitment augments or diminishes the value of a firm. Some researchers have found that the market rewards a company's environmental performance (Yamaguchi, 2008; Aktas et al., 2011; Al-Najjar & Anfimiadou, 2012), while other studies have found negative or insignificant results (Hsu & Wang, 2013; Ramiah et al., 2013). Moreover, some researchers have found that shareholders react positively to eco-friendly corporate initiatives (Flammer, 2013; Klassen & McLaughlin, 1996), while others have noticed that the announcement of voluntary emission reduction has a negative impact on a firm's market value (Jacobs et al., 2010; Fisher-Vandem & Thorburn, 2008)

The relatively new awareness of environmental concerns has its shortcomings in terms of data availability and quality. This explains the inconclusiveness of the results and emphasizes the complexity of considering environmental and financial performance simultaneously. Stronger results in both quality and quantity about this relationship can be obtained in the field of corporate social responsibility (CSR). The original focus of CSR has been on social issues. However, as the concept of CSR is continually changing and adapting to the corporate's surroundings (Carroll & Shabana, 2010), the environment has become an integral part of CSR (Sprinkle & Maines, 2010).

The relationship between financial and societal performance has been subject to over two hundred studies (Wang et al., 2016). A meta-analysis on 109 studies conducted by Margolis & Walsh (2003) found that approximately 50% of the studies that use corporate social performance as an independent variable displayed a positive relationship between financial and societal performance, while only 7% demonstrated a negative relationship. In a more recent literature overview, Clark & Viehs (2014) concluded that financial markets pay some attention to the societal performance of a company. In fact, the majority of current studies have found a slight but positive relationship between social and financial performance (Beurden & Gossling, 2008; Chi-shiun et al., 2010; Servaes & Tamayo, 2013; Bukit et al., 2018).

There exist, however, important limitations to these findings. Noise in financial markets can lead to an excessive market valuation of companies perceived as socially responsible (Orlitzky, 2013). Many characteristics such as the market factor, market capitalization or past returns may influence a firm's financial performance and affect the results of such research (Fama & French, 1993; Lakonishok et al., 1994). Additionally, several scholars have considered these findings to be biased and inconsistent because of a two-way relationship between social and financial performance (Telle, 2006; Nakao et al., 2007; Wagner & Wehrmeyer, 2002).

Based on previous findings, no evidence of a significantly positive relationship exists between climate commitment and financial performance. Therefore, with business leaders' focus on profit maximization, these previous findings do not appear to give sufficient financial motivation for companies to invest in mitigation or adaptation measures.

2.3.2 Recent developments

Despite the deceiving results of previous studies, over 1,300 companies have publicly pledged to commit to climate change over the last five years through the We Mean Business coalition, a partnership between the most influential international nonprofit organizations that address climate change. This coalition supports and supervises climate initiatives that incite companies to act sooner and beyond their governments' environmental pledges.⁶

⁶ <https://www.wemeanbusinesscoalition.org/companies/> (Description of initiatives and companies committed)

The Science-Based Targets is an initiative that mobilizes companies to establish emissions targets in line with keeping the temperature rise below 2° C and sets precise policies to define a company's pathway to achieve its objectives. As of August 2020, over 960 firms have publicly joined the initiative, and over a quarter of the signatories have aligned their commitments to limit the global temperature rise to 1.5° C (SBTi, 2019). Among the largest and most ambitious companies are Unilever, which has pledged to invest EUR 1 billion in climate funds and to achieve net-zero emissions for all its products by 2039; IKEA, which has committed to reduce its absolute GHG emissions across its value chain by at least 15% by 2030; and Sony, which has pledged to decrease its GHG emissions from operations by 42% by 2020 and to reduce its environmental footprint to zero by 2050⁷. In addition, through the EP100 initiative, more than 250 companies including Apple, Facebook and Nike have committed to doubling their energy productivity within 25 years. Through the RE100 initiative, over 90 business firms, including Alphabet, Apple and eBay have pledged to use only renewable energy by 2030. Finally, over 50 companies including Carrefour, L'Oréal and Nestlé have announced through the Zero Deforestation initiative to only use commodities produced without deforestation.

The companies engaged in these four initiatives could reduce global GHG emissions by 3.2 to 4.2 gigatons per year by 2030 (CDP, 2016), which is equivalent to 7-9% of the global emissions of 2018. These numbers may appear promising compared to the actual 7.6% cut required per year to reach the 1.5° C threshold cited before (UNEP, 2019). However, the CDP's forecast has some limitations. The projection is based on the condition that each company will achieve its ambitious goals and the number of firms that will join the initiatives by 2030 has been optimistically forecasted. The most concerning part is that companies' commitments to climate change almost exclusively concern mitigation measures.

As of 2020, only meager and scattered evidence that companies have engaged in adaptation measures exists. For example, Bloomberg has relocated one of its data centers to protect its installations against flooding. Maersk, a shipping company, has studied how to increase the ports' resilience to rising oceans. E. ON, an energy company, has announced it will cease all its traditional electricity producing activities to focus exclusively on renewable energy. Eskom, also active in the energy industry, has integrated adaptation analysis and responses into its existing practices. When an economical agent augments its resilience to climate change, such

⁷ <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/companies-taking-action/> (More information on companies' commitments)

as through the previous examples, the adaptability of the whole society increases and the transition to a more sustainable economy is promoted (UNEP, 2012; Cloutier et al., 2014; Berrang-Ford et al., 2014). Therefore, companies exclusively engaging in mitigation is an issue for the global response to climate change. One should question the reasons why businesses prefer to engage in mitigation measures.

2.3.3 Financial performance and mitigation

Investing in climate mitigation to meet economic objectives is in line with the company's responsibility to maximize the long-term wealth of the shareholders (Jensen, 2002). This means that businesses engaged in social activities expect a recognition for their efforts. Therefore, business leaders may consider climate commitment as a strategic weapon to increase the corporate's wealth (Garriga & Melé, 2004), to reinforce the company's level of brand protection (Polonsky et al., 2011) or to further the firm's financial performance (Bhattacharya et al., 2009).

Studies have found that competitive advantages, an important strategic resource for a firm's notoriety, can be obtained through investments in societal issues (Park et al., 2014; Naqvi, 2013). A company is said to have a competitive advantage when "it is implementing a value creating strategy not simultaneously being implemented by any current or potential player" (Barney, 1991, p102). Therefore, mitigation strategies are not sustainable competitive advantages since they are already implemented by numerous companies and can be easily replicated. This entails that companies having already improved their environmental performance may receive a first mover advantage (Fisher-Vanden & Thorburn, 2011) but the financial incentives for late movers are uncertain.

In fact, to establish its ideal degree of mitigation, a company optimizes the trade-off between the costs to reduce its emissions and the benefits from its commitment (Hjort, 2016). Therefore, this trade-off may remain negative over time since the financial advantages to engage mitigation measures tend to erode. This observation could influence business leaders framed on profit maximization not to commit to climate change. Based exclusively on a financial rationale, only a minority of companies should be expected to reduce their GHG emissions voluntarily. This analysis is probably the reason why the We Mean Business climate coalition counts approximately 1,300 firms engaged in climate mitigation in August 2020, when the number of multinational companies has been estimated to be over 100,000 (Jaworek & Kuzel, 2015).

Therefore, the search to receive a market recognition for companies mitigating their emissions is a serious hurdle to the global response to climate change.

2.3.4 Financial performance and adaptation

Adaptation is a strategy of anticipating the constraints and opportunities of climate change. It consists in evaluating the firm's vulnerability related to the supply chain, the production chain, the suppliers and the customers with respect to the various climate-related risks. Each company has to find its most pertinent reasons to adapt, which could be the sensitivity of its infrastructures to violent climatic events, the exposure to climate-related regulatory measures or the modification of its customers' demand (Sussman & Freed, 2008). To facilitate the tasks, tools exist such as the Preview Global Risk Data Platform that provides information and spatial data about risks from natural hazards, the European climate adaptation platform Climate-ADAPT that shares data and information to support the adaptation for European countries, or weADAPT, a global scale platform.

Adaptation is not only an environmental imperative. Economic benefits are expected from an efficient strategy (UNGC, 2011; UNEP, 2012) and each economic agent - ranging from craftspeople to multinationals - has interests to adapt (Wedawatta & Ingirige, 2012). By revising its exposure, a company will reduce its weaknesses, which in turn enables the firm to rely strongly on its current activities. Adaptation is a sustainable competitive advantage since it is a proof of the competitiveness, the innovation capacity and the good governance of a company (GCA, 2019). In contrast with mitigation, the interests of adaptation measures have a purely egoistic nature since they benefit the companies undertaking them. Therefore, the low percentage of businesses developing adaptation strategies is surprising.

The first reason for this inaction is derived from the definition of adaptation. An efficient adaptation strategy is one in which the effects of climate change are invisible (Euzen et al., 2017). This contrasts with mitigation measures, where the benefits to society are quantifiable and therefore easier to be publicly recognized (Agrawala et al., 2011). Indeed, the benefits to engage in adaptation measures are private and local, therefore, adaptation does not conform within the standard CSR narratives. Thus, fewer market recognition opportunities exist in adaptation compared to mitigation strategies.

The second reason for this inaction is that companies' classical tool to account for the value of time is the discount rate. The higher the discount rate, the lower the net present value of future benefits. Yet, the reduction of a company's vulnerability to climate change implies expenses in the present, while the benefits of an efficient adaptation strategy materialize on a long-term horizon. Therefore, the long-term advantages of adaptation measures exceed the horizon of the prevailing focus on immediate profit and short-term projects (Caldecott & McDaniels, 2014). This explains why business leaders' short-termism is an immense hurdle to the global response to climate change (Biesbrock et al., 2011; Hjort, 2016).

2.3.5 Corporate performance

The principal obstacle for a sufficient response from companies to climate change is the actual measure of corporate performance, based on a financial perspective. As long as business leaders' fiduciary responsibility is orientated exclusively to the maximization of their shareholders' wealth (Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004), the firms' expenses to mitigate or adapt to climate change will remain marginal compared to the climate crisis. Because in such circumstances, companies perceive climate commitment as an effort. This observation is alarming because during difficult times such as the 2019 feeble growth prospects (WEF, 2020) or the 2020 pandemic, these efforts could be postponed to more advantageous days. Yet, climate change does not wait.

Overall, this demonstrates the ineffectiveness of market incentives for firms' consideration of climate change on a private and voluntary basis. Due to the actual definition of corporate performance, one should not expect businesses' investments in mitigation or adaptation measures to be sufficient to cope with climate change.

2.4 Financial performance and climate non-commitment

This chapter analyses the external pressures that could force a company to commit to climate change due to the adverse impact climate-related risks weigh on their financial performance. These constraints stem from legal authorities, civil society and a company's financial environment and the climate-related risks are classified as litigation, reputation and divestment risks.

2.4.1 Financial performance and legal risk

Business leaders are expected to focus on their shareholders' profits, within the limits of the legal constraints in the countries where they operate (Friedman, 1970). This means that companies do not have financial incentives to act beyond their legal obligations. However, the absence of international legal constraints is an issue for the regulation of international companies (Beck, 2000). This is why public regulation is an indispensable tool to restrain companies' negative externalities on society.

The complexity of regulating private actors in relation to environmental issues is rooted in the concept of responsibility, which is one of the most complicated and elusive philosophical notions (Goodpaster, 1983). To attribute an act to a person or an entity, proof of accountability must exist. The extent of the responsibility depends on what laws are considering to be part of the company's sphere of influence. For example, from the moment the causal relationship between climate-related damages and a specific firm's GHG emission is established, a company will have to account for its responsibility on climate change. Thus, new environmental regulations are risks that can impact companies' profitability.

Legal risk is defined as the risk of financial or reputational damages that result from lack of awareness or indifferences to the way that law and regulation apply to a firm's businesses, processes, products or services (Whalley, 2016). Legal risk has become a threat to multinational companies since the adoption of the United Nation's major text in 2011 (UN, 2011). The text's guiding principles related to human rights and transnational companies have established a framework for the activities of multinational firms. Although these principles are not binding, they have paved the way for legal actions. As a result, lawsuits have become an important lever to accelerate governments and companies' commitments to climate change (Villavicencio Calzadilla, 2019).

Climate change litigation has grown exponentially from a few cases in the 1990s to more than 1,300 cases across 28 countries at the beginning of 2019 (Setzer & Vanhala; 2019). A major breakthrough occurred with the Urgenda case in 2015, in which the Dutch government was sued for not safeguarding its citizens from climate change. As a result, the country has announced the complete closing of its coal mines by 2030 and has pledged to reduce its national

GHG emissions by 49% by 2030 (Leijten, 2019). The momentum generated by the Urgenda case has led to identical cases in the courts of several countries (Ganguly et al., 2018), including the Rocky Hill case in Australia, in which a new coal mine program has been refused due to its inconsistency with the country's pledge at the Paris Agreement (Hughes, 2019) and the Juliana case in 2019 that aims to halt the U.S. government's financial support of fossil fuels (Levy; 2019).

However, climate litigation does not apply exclusively to governments. Companies are also being held directly accountable for their implications in climate-related disasters (Peel et al., 2017). The responsibility of a private company for its share in climate change was acknowledged for the first time in 2016 (Frank et al., 2019). The Court of Appeals accepted the case of a Peruvian citizen who sued an energy company for its contribution to increasing the risk of a lagoon flooding due to glacial retreat. In 2018, over a thousand Filipinos survivors of the typhoon Haiyan were assisted by 12 NGOs and filed a petition to the human rights court. They asked for an investigation to establish the connection between the GHG emissions of 47 major carbon emitting companies and the rise of extreme climatic events (Greenpeace, 2019). Although the Philippines Human Rights Commission did not impose fines or force the defendants to reduce their emissions, it declared that fossil fuel corporations may be found legally responsible for harming human rights through climate change.

Assuredly, the companies' responsibility for climate change seems legitimate. The raise in disasters due to natural hazards over the past decades has largely been attributed to the increase of GHG concentration in the atmosphere (Van Aalst, 2006; Rahmstorf and Coumou, 2011) and over 70% of the global GHG emissions from 1988-2015 have been ascribed to 100 active fossil fuel producers (CDP, 2017).

The cases cited above opened the door for further litigation (Setzer & Benjamin, 2019) and recent scientific findings are being translated into relevant proof in court (Pfrommer et al., 2019). This means that, in the future, major contributors to climate change could be forced to pay compensations for the costs their activities generated on the environment and society. Therefore, due to litigations, the impact of climate non-commitment could be disastrous for the financial performance of the most emitting companies.

Limitations exist to the use of litigation as a strategy to tackle climate change. Particularly, attributing the monetary losses from a specific climate-related event to the cumulative CO₂ emissions of a distinct firm is an immense scientific challenge (Harrington, 2019). Moreover, the timeframe for the effects of litigation to manifest can take years given the lengthy process that legal actions usually require within the court system (Peel & Osofsky, 2020). Therefore, litigation is an essential but imperfect strategy to mitigate global GHG emissions.

In addition, litigation and reputation risks are closely connected. Corporate scandals such as Enron (Watkins, 2003), Unilever, P&G and Nestlé's use of palm oil (Greenpeace, 2007) or the BP's Deepwater (McKillop, 2010) are examples that a company's failure to be a good corporate citizen significantly impacts the firms' reputation, which in turn impacts its market value.

The episode known as the Dieseltgate illustrates that legal processes can also damage the reputation and financial performance of a whole industry (Bouzzine & Lueg, 2020). In the three days following the disclosure of emission violations in Volkswagen diesel vehicles, the German company's stock price fell from USD 160 to USD 110 (Snyder & Jones, 2015). Beyond the direct impact on Volkswagen's market value, consequences of the announcement were also felt amongst their commercial partners and other reputable German brands. Fracarolli Nunes and Lee Park (2016) estimated that the total market value penalization of Volkswagen's industry peers was close to USD 6.44 billion. This demonstrates the financial damages litigation and reputation risks weigh on companies and industries that do not conform to the environmental regulations or do not anticipate these risks.

The possible financial repercussions of companies or industries particularly exposed to climate change induce behavioral responses among related institutions and investors. Therefore, finance has a role to play in the global response to climate change.

2.4.2 Financial performance and divestment risk

In recent years, financial practitioners and regulators have acknowledged the important economic damage a transition to a low-carbon economy could cause to the industry of non-renewable energy (Mercure et al., 2018). However, the impressive growth of divestment from non-renewable stocks was mainly driven by NGOs' strategy to accuse and pressure investors

to drop their fossil fuel stocks in favor of greener alternatives (Ayling & Gunningham, 2015). As a result, approximately 1,000 institutional investors with USD 6.24 trillion of assets under management discarded their assets in fossil energies in 2018 (Arbelle Advisors, 2018). The divestment movement added a social pressure to investors and institutions to be socially and environmentally responsible. Yet, investors' search for sustainable investments is not recent.

Sustainable and responsible investments (SRI) is an ethical tendency that emerged around 1980, stemming from investors' interests to include social criteria in their portfolio without renouncing their profits. Nowadays, the financial power of impactful and sustainable investments is impressive. In 2018, sustainable investing assets in the five major markets were USD 30.7 trillion, representing 49% and 26% of the total managed asset in Europe and United-States respectively (GSIR, 2018). However, a sustainable and responsible investor cannot be presumed to be identical to a socially responsible individual since the former's profit-seeking nature is undeniable. Sustainable and responsible investments are financial industry products and do not defend the values of CSR or durability (Déjean, 2005). In fact, these investments may compensate for an egoistic way-of-life (Rosen et al., 1991) and could lead to a dilution of the necessity for a more responsible behavior (Covington & Thamotheram 2014). Although the ethical nature of sustainable investments is highly questionable, SRIs have played an important role to promote companies' communications policies concerning their exposure to climate change.

Initiatives such as the Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) have been developed in response for investors' demand to disclose firms' climate-related risks. The TCFD is supervised by the We Mean Business coalition and aims at disclosing clear and comparable information on the financial risk climate change weighs on companies. As of August 2020, over 450 businesses with a market capitalization of USD 7.9 trillion have supported the initiative. The fact that financial markets can incorporate information about a company's climate-related risks transfers the risks to investors (ABI, 2004). This offers incentives for individuals and institutions to choose stocks from companies and industries that are resilient to the consequences of climate change. As a result, the impact on financial performance of companies that did not reduce their exposure to climate change can be significant due to investors' divestment.

2.4.3 Financial performance and climate-related risks

Legal risks cause substantial financial uncertainty on the major contributors to anthropic GHG emissions. When the causal relationship between climate-related loss and damage and a firm's emissions is established, the companies that emit the most will have to pay for their activities' externalities on society. This is why legal risks have a significant role in compelling firms to take consistent actions in line with international climate targets (Carnwath, 2016). Accordingly, the shares and bonds issued by companies exposed to climate-related risks are less attractive to institutional and private investors. Thus, if firms do not anticipate litigation, reputation and divestment risks, the impact of climate non-commitment on their financial performance may be detrimental.

Strong limitations remain on the effectiveness of climate-related risks to incite companies to commit to climate change. First, litigation and reputation risks principally punish companies that causes the most environmental damage. This means that only a minority of firms are exposed to these risks. In this perspective, climate commitment of companies not particularly exposed will remain insufficient. Second, climate-related risks are likely to be substantially underestimated (Goldstein et al., 2019). Investors are likely to be broadly unconvinced about the adverse impact of climate change on their investments (Covington & Thamotheram 2014). Thus, divestment risks are unimportant for companies not particularly exposed. Third, litigation risks may never materialize (Harrington, 2019) and since companies maximize their profits within the limits of their legal environment, the investments in mitigation or adaptation measures will remain inadequate. Therefore, based on the impact on financial performance, climate-related risks do not appear to be sufficient motives for companies to address the climate crisis.

2.5 Conclusion on financial performance

Businesses, as the intermediaries between individuals' needs and consumption, have an essential role to play in the global response to climate change. However, on a voluntary and private basis, the companies' commitments are not sufficient to cope with climate change. As long as climate commitment is perceived as an effort from companies, business leaders calculate how investments in mitigation or adaptation strategies will affect their income. As a

result, firms' commitment will remain disproportionate compared to the climate crisis. This is especially relevant in difficult times, when a company's liquidity is logically oriented towards what managers believe to be their priority, thus, not the climate. Accordingly, neither legal risks, targeting a minority of companies, nor divestment risks, generally underestimated, are sufficient external pressures to permit the necessary changes.

Therefore, the coexistence of contradictory intentions such as shareholder value maximization and environmental commitment within the same organization demonstrates the limits of considering financial performance of a company as a primary indicator of corporate welfare when humanity faces a climate crisis.

Given the impacts and irreversible nature of climate change, any possible solution will require to consider the evidence: companies' approach to the issue must change. To manage an adequate response to a global crisis, with economic, environmental and social ramifications, the first step is to recognize that the actual economic models do not encapsulate the size of this challenge. Since the definitions of corporate performance and responsibility depend upon the general conviction regarding the objectives to be achieved, the question is to know towards which direction companies should be orientated.

3 PERFORMANCE AND RESPONSIBILITY

3.1 Inequalities

Income inequality in OECD countries is currently at the highest level in the past fifty years (OECD, 2019). Evidence suggests that in countries where income inequalities have increased, wealth inequalities have grown even faster (Davies & Shorrocks, 2018). Although inequalities are almost inevitable in a market-based economic system, an excessive gap between income levels among citizens has an adverse impact on a country's response to climate change. Previous research suggests that trust and civic participation are low in unequal societies (Uslaner & Brown 2005; Alesina & La Ferrara 2000) and that social participation differs greatly between low- and high-income households (Lancee & Van de Werfhorst, 2011). Since social cohesion and fairness are powerful levers to bring together a population toward a common target (Grimalda & Tänzler, 2018), wealth and income inequalities among countries are obstacles for the population to participate in the global response to climate change.

Middle-to-low income countries, which encompass more than 70% of the world's population, are currently responsible for over 50% of the global GHG emissions (Oliver et al., 2014). In addition, such countries' population and energy consumption are expected to grow by 25% and 50% respectively, by 2050 (EIA, 2019; UN, 2019). Therefore, to reduce the impacts of climate change at a global level, these countries must prioritize mitigation and adaptation measures. This suggests that emerging countries must develop climate-resilient, cleaner, thus, more expensive economic models than the ones industrialized countries have developed. However, the populations of numerous emerging countries are facing more urgent threats such as starvation, water scarcity, and poverty. The billions of human beings who are exposed to such situations will logically focus on the short-term satisfaction of their needs and will disregard the long-term consequences of climate change. Therefore, inequality among countries is a hurdle for the global response to climate change.

Moreover, the poorest countries are the most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change (Adger et al., 2007) and are also the countries that did the least to cause it. This particular situation is why industrialized countries and businesses must give a greater attention to social justice and help emerging countries to adapt to climate change. In addition, ensuring resilience

of poorer regions and countries has numerous benefits. Sustainable management and preservation of fertile lands are not only the best economic remedies for the vulnerability of highly exposed regions, but they also ensure global food and energy security and contributes to reducing conflicts, creating jobs, and diminishing forced migration (Prahalad & Hammond, 2002).

Therefore, climate change intensifies inequalities between the rich and the poor, and inequalities are significant obstacles for the global response to climate change. This vicious circle underlines that before being economic, the challenge of climate change is social. An efficient strategy to respond to this issue must connect environmental justice with social justice, and this must be accomplished at a global level.

The strength of the narrative of climate change lays in its global reach. In the scientific discourses, rising global temperatures and the changing global climate system result in global warming. This phenomenon contrasts with the local manifestations of the weather and has shifted the common understanding of the climate to a more globalized approach (Hulme, 2010). Citizens around the world have come to understand that they are intimate collaborators in the mutual shaping of the present and future climate. Furthermore, the cosmopolitan nature of climate change transcends countries' borders, cultures and beliefs. These cosmopolitan characteristics also belongs to multinational companies. In addition, climate change has a social, economic and global nature, and so do have multinational firms. Therefore, to permit an efficient response to climate change, companies must endorse social responsibilities at a global level. This is what the field of CSR attempted to accomplish.

3.2 Corporate social responsibility

The social consequences of repeated restructuring and uncompensated job losses in the 1970s tarnished public opinion about the world's largest firms. As a reaction, these companies attempted to restore their loss of trust and legitimacy by seeking moral and symbolic rights to justify their operations. Business leaders understood that to obtain a license to operate, being perceived as socially responsible (Burchell & Cook, 2006) or at least giving the impression of being active in social and responsible activities was fundamental (Greenwood, 2007). This

search for legitimacy is how the explicit conception of the corporate social responsibility has emerged.

In 1991, Carroll introduced the pyramid of CSR and placed the economic responsibility at the pyramid's base. This positioning underlines that being profitable is imperative for a firm and represents the foundation upon which the entire company rests. The second tier belongs to legal responsibilities. Laws are crucial for a company since they are the codification of what is right or wrong for the society. The third and fourth layers, respectively the ethical and philanthropic responsibilities, indicate that firms are expected to go beyond the society's normative expectations. Decades after the development of Carroll's pyramid, scholars are still debating and adjusting the companies' fundamental duties. The constant evolution of societal and environmental practices makes it difficult to universally define the concept of CSR, and the lack of a precise definition incites to deepen its meaning. This explains why Dahlsrud (2008) identified no less than 37 different interpretations of CSR. These numerous definitions ended up generating complexity for the managerial operability of CSR.

The concept of sustainable development has been popularized after the UN's Brundtland report in 1987, which argues that "the 'environment' is where we live; and 'development' is what we all do in attempting to improve our lot within that abode. The two are inseparable" (UN, 1987, p7). A decade after the Brundtland report, Elkington (1999) proposed the concept of triple bottom line that illustrated the three pillars of a sustainable company: profits, planet, and people. Elkington highlighted that the performance of a company is not exclusively based on financial criteria, but also includes social and environmental standards. As a result, the triple bottom line concept helped transpose sustainable development to the field of managerial science and enabled the managerial operability of CSR (Kuhlman & Farrington, 2010).

However, traditional CSR discourses include characteristics that complicate an adequate integration of environmental and social issues in companies' practices. Perrow (2000) described CSR as a mechanism whose net outcome is to position a company to better profit from its environment. Jensen (2002) reaffirmed the primacy of shareholders by arguing that the inclusion of stakeholders' interests was essential for long-term value maximization. Garriga & Melé (2004) justify that companies should use CSR as a strategic weapon to respond to market forces or legal constraints, and Carroll & Shabana (2010) argues that a firm must assess if investing in CSR is in line with its economic objectives. Therefore, the neoclassic theory that

considers any finality other than shareholders' profits maximization to be subversive is tenacious in the debates about CSR.

As a result, the concept of CSR faces the same obstacles that inhibit companies to commit to climate change on a private and voluntary basis. If businesses assume social responsibilities only if the action advances their long-term market value (Mackey et al., 2007), companies' investments in mitigation or adaptation measures will remain insufficient. Therefore, the concept of CSR only treats a few symptoms of the issues, without attacking the root of the problem: maintaining corporate performance for both environmental and financial goals is impractical. From a financial perspective, many corporate decisions related to climate change are not presented as potential win-wins, but rather as dilemmas (Badaracco, 1997) and through dilemmas, viewpoints, values, and interests collide (Davis et al., 1998). Therefore, corporate responsibility and performance must be defined differently.

3.3 The corporate responsibility

3.3.1 The blurring limit between the economy and politics

The neoliberal public organization is structured under three distinct dimensions: civil society, the politic body, and the economy (Habermas, 1998). Political authority, in particular the government, represents the people, protects social justice, and provides public goods. In the economic sphere, business firms and households focus on their private interests by following the rules established by the government. Civil society expresses values, interests, and rights in public discussions and manifestations. In this configuration, the state system is the sole political institution that focuses on the welfare of the society, while economic agents are expected to focus exclusively on their profits (Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004). Therefore, the material world (i.e., the economic sphere) and the ideological world (i.e., the political sphere) are commonly perceived as a dichotomy. However, this conception ignores an important element: the economic pole may have an adverse impact on the welfare of the population.

Financial incentives to reduce production costs have invited businesses to relocate a significant part of their operations in foreign locations with generally poor legal systems, fragile democracies, and corruption (Scherer & Palazzo, 2011). Globalization has given multinational

companies the opportunity to reduce their expenses and to escape their territorial jurisdiction. As a result, the regulation of the global economy has become problematic for states and international institutions. The increasing failure of the states' capacity to regulate the firms' transnational activities and to reduce their negative externalities on society has cast doubts upon the legitimacy of the states' duty to serve the general interest in a globalized world (Beck, 2000; Habermas, 2001).

Moreover, since the 1980s, states have been accused of allocating and using public resources inefficiently in many developed countries. This indictment has resulted in a reduction of public expenditures, cuts in the public sector jobs, and the underfunding of social programs and infrastructures (Bruch & White 2018; Lobao et al., 2014). Such political reorganizations have led to a diminution of the role of the state and, in turn, to a privatization of services usually assumed by the government (Crouch, 2009). The retreat of the state and the diversion of resources to the private sector have left a part of the population deprived of public services, which has increased inequalities (Lobao et al., 2018). This transition has contributed to fracturing the social contract between states, economic agents, and citizens. Therefore, the states' discard of political responsibilities has induced new models of the relationship between state and non-state actors (Lopez-Santana, 2015).

Political ideologies have also impacted the role of states. The dominance of neoliberal economies since the 1970s has influenced the West's answer to societal issues by hyper-individualist and atomistic approaches (Bendell, 2018). The election of Donald Trump and Brexit in 2016 are striking examples of the growth of individualism in industrialized countries. Additionally, the escalation of worldwide trade conflicts has amplified national isolationism and damaged an already feeble economic landscape (OECD, 2019; WEF, 2020). Yet, political tensions, neo-liberal discourses, and individualism incite countries to withdraw from their pledges to fight climate change, as has happened with the Trump Administration (Adler, 2018). This is why Harari (2018, p156) argues that “[n]ational isolationism is probably even more dangerous in the context of climate change than of nuclear war”.

The states' incapacity to regulate transnational corporations, their voluntary retreat from duties that previously belonged exclusively to the government, and the growth of individualism highlights the imperative need for reflection on the political role of the state. This assessment is especially relevant given the current environmental situation. States' failure to respond to

climate change signals the need to give a greater role to businesses to resolve issues of public goods.

The economic power of the world's largest firms is a strong example of the influence that companies have on society. In 2016, in terms of USD billion revenue per year, 69 of the 100 largest economic entities in the world were business firms⁸. As examples, Walmart was ranked 10th between Canada and Spain, and Glencore, known for its adverse environmental impacts, was ranked 38th between Turkey and Denmark. In addition to their economic power, firms' activities, public discourses, and lobbying influence institutions, politics and citizens in the area they operate (Hillman et al., 2006; Dunning, 2009). When a company's activity or decision has an impact beyond its direct environment and affects others, this entity possesses political powers. Therefore, the economic and politic spheres are not categorically separated; rather, they increasingly overlap.

The conventional approach of CSR relies on the assumptions of strong governmental institutions and a clear separation between economy and politics (Scherer, 2018). To respond to the regulatory vacuum opening around the practices of multinational companies, the recent geopolitical changes, and the failure of CSR to incorporate the dynamics of states and companies given in this chapter, scholars have introduced the concept of the political corporate social responsibility (political CSR; see Scherer & Palazzo, 2007, 2011).

3.3.2 Political corporate social responsibility

The failure of local governments to address basic human rights and to implement legal regulations as well as the transfer of public governance duties to private agents has incited businesses to endorse political responsibilities that were previously regarded to be exclusively assumed by the government (Rasche & Kell, 2010; Wood & Wright, 2015). Over the last few decades, companies have responded to social issues such as illiteracy, famine, or illnesses (Margolis & Walsh, 2003), have defended human rights (Matten & Crane, 2005; Hsieh, 2004), as well as committed to climate change (Kolk & Pinske, 2005). These actions confirm that businesses have voluntarily engaged in self-regulation to fill the governance gap left by states (Vogel, 2008; McGuire, 2013). In such circumstances, companies have assumed the

⁸ <https://www.globaljustice.org.uk/news/2018/oct/17/69-richest-100-entities-planet-are-corporations-not-governments-figures-show> (List of the 100 largest economic entities)

responsibility to provide goods whose nature in terms of accessibility, quality and affordability have a political character.

The definition of politic involves public deliberations and decisions about collective issues, the production of public goods (or the prevention of public bads), and the contribution to the social welfare (Scherer et al. 2014, 2016). Therefore, political CSR logically supports the idea that companies are behaving like political actors. Scherer & Palazzo (2007, 2011) have explained that the concept of political CSR is an extended model of governance in which businesses provide public goods and is understood as the decision for companies to assume state-like political responsibilities to respond to social or environmental issues.

Moreover, companies engaged in political CSR are not driven by economic motivations; they aim to directly resolve social issues in a legitimate and responsible manner. The incentives that motivate businesses to engage proactively stem from altruistic moral concerns (Baron, 2010) or pro-social motivations (Bénabou & Tirole, 2010). Such firms do not seek a competitive advantage or profit maximization (Cetindamar & Husoy, 2007), but are committed to contribute positively to the social welfare.

The concept of political CSR challenges the common conception of the role of the company in society. Therefore, concerns are raised about sharing political responsibilities between states and companies. In contrast to the political system, businesses are not bounded by a direct democratic authority. By assuming political responsibilities, business leaders could determine the interests of society and unilaterally choose their company's contribution to the issues of public goods. Therefore, without proper democratic deliberations about the society's needs, companies engaged in political CSR could face issues of legitimacy (Scherer et al. 2013) and efficiency (Besley & Ghatak 2007). Thus, “[r]esearch on political CSR must not restrain itself to descriptive and explanatory research but has to build on a solid value base” (Scherer, 2018, p394).

3.3.3 Political corporate social responsibility and climate change

Stabilizing the climate involves developing a response that must be globalized to be effective. Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach with a strong connection between economic, environmental and social justice must be adopted; this approach is political. Climate change

requires companies and business leaders to reshape the economic models at the local, national and global level. In each situation, problems and obstacles are faced that require new technologies, models, and tools that have yet to be explored; this situation is also political.

Simultaneously, businesses have voluntarily assumed the responsibilities of a political nature due to the states' incapacity to regulate international companies, retreat from public duties, and failure to respond to societal issues, including climate change. Thus, companies have started to endorse a political role to respond to social, environmental, economic, and global problems, which are also the attributes of climate change.

Scherer & Palazzo (2007, 2011) have introduced the concept of political CSR, which is an extended model of governance that explains companies' increasing contribution to public goods. Therefore, the concept of political CSR responds to the issue of defining a role for corporations in a society experiencing a climate crisis. Some concerns exist regarding the fact that climate change may be too important to be solely addressed by people who are not exclusively devoted to it (Giddens, 2009). However, the concept of political CSR is applied in a context in which governments are unable to fulfil their duties, and climate change is one of them.

3.4 The corporate performance

3.4.1 Corporate governance

The question of finding legitimate and democratic models to control companies assuming political responsibilities moves center stage. Any possible answer to this question must include changes at the level of corporate governance (Scherer et al., 2014). Corporate management must extend its frame of reference from the sole focus on shareholders to consider individual and collective interests to find the equilibrium between economic and social objectives (Gomez & Korine, 2005).

Accordingly, global governance initiatives have been developed to improve corporate disclosure and achieve stakeholder's accountability (Hess, 2007). These initiatives have responded to stakeholders' demands for transparent disclosure on companies' environmental

and social impacts (Hansen & Schaltegger, 2017). The goal of these multiple stakeholders' governance initiatives is to set effective and unified systems of reporting to permit comparison across companies. As a result, businesses have expanded their reporting to include extra-financial information on how they fulfill their social and environmental responsibilities (Owen, 2008).

The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is the most frequently adopted sustainability reporting guideline (Fernandez-Feijoo et al., 2014). The GRI Standards provide a set of indicators for the economic, environmental, and social performance of a company and aims to make social and environmental reporting on par with financial reporting (Sasse-Werhahn, 2019). However, the GRI has been criticized for its inadequacy with the fundamental principles of sustainability (Isaksson & Steimle, 2009). The lack of consistent measures hinders firms' ability to credibly account for their contribution to the global welfare. Therefore, a need exists for more holistic and humanistic governance metrics (Waddock, 2016), in which businesses can account for their contribution to create or preserve public goods. In other words, metrics should be created to uphold the principles of political CSR.

3.4.2 The sustainable value-added metric

The prevailing techniques to internalize a company's externalities are primarily directed at punishing firms' negative impact on society. To do so, economists have generally advocated placing burden-oriented taxes on companies (Baumol, 1972; Fullerton & Kim, 2006; Barrage, 2020). These approaches do not account for firms' contribution to global welfare. Therefore, the true measure of corporate performance would be better approximated by a new metric of economic sustainability that includes the companies' contribution to natural and social capital (Costanza, 2009). In this perspective, sustainability includes long-term economic, environmental, and social factors and aims at maintaining the firm's economic, natural and social capital (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002). In other words, to be sustainable, businesses have to create or preserve public goods.

Bardy (2018) expands the view on capital maintenance through the development of the economic value added (EVA) to be what he calls the sustainable value added (SVA). The EVA is a well-established metric of the overall financial performance of a company, based on the fact that shareholders gain when the return of capital engaged is higher than the cost of that

capital (Dodd & Chen, 1997). From this definition, Bardy & Massaro argue that “[b]ased on pure logic, all stakeholders of a corporation gain when the value created by a corporation is greater than the cost of the capital employed in the corporation and of the capital/the assets employed outside the corporation” (Bardy & Massaro, 2015, p501). The resulting equation is the following:

$$SVA = \text{Capital engaged in economic resources} - \text{cost of capital engaged in economic resources} - \text{cost of capital engaged in ecological resources} - \text{cost of capital engaged in social resources}$$

or

$$SVA = EVA - \text{cost of capital engaged in ecological resources} - \text{cost of capital engaged in social resources}$$

Ecological resources are, for example, the access to water and fresh air or the possibility to pollute public water and air. Social resources include the quality of the legal and educational systems, the access to a working labor market and to public infrastructures.

Bardy’s metric is similar to integrating the external costs of companies consuming public goods (Bardy, 2018); thus, this metric is also burden orientated. The equation may be modified to also account for a company’s participation in the creation or preservation of public goods. Therefore, I have developed an updated version of Bardy’s equation:

$$SVA = EVA + \text{capital invested in ecological resources} - \text{cost of capital engaged in ecological resources} + \text{capital invested in social resources} - \text{cost of capital engaged in social resources}$$

or

$$SVA = \text{Economic Value Added} + \text{Ecological Value Added} + \text{Social Value Added}$$

The ecological value added is the company’s externalities on the environment. Companies’ commitments to safeguard the environment are accounted for positively, while companies’ adverse effects on the environment, such as GHG emissions or water pollution are accounted for negatively. Accordingly, the social value added is the balance between the company’s negative and positive impacts on social factors such as civil infrastructures, public health, or education. This metric is especially applicable in the context of climate change. The engagements in mitigation measures account for the capital invested in ecological resources,

while the investments in adaptation measures account for the capital invested in social resources.

The global use of this metric would set the stage for a societal consensus in which companies are more than economic entities whose purpose is to generate shareholder wealth. Creating value with the sustainable value-added metric would signify creating public value. Therefore, with this metric, a company's purpose is to maximize the society's welfare, and its performance is based on how efficiently it improves financial, social and environmental capital. This paradigm should be the definition of corporate performance.

Nevertheless, a significant obstacle exists to the use of the sustainable value-added metric. Companies' use of public goods are rarely measured in monetary terms since their valuation has not reached the position of being generally accepted and applicable (Bardy, 2018). However, initiatives supported by the Big Four⁹ to conceive common and consistent metrics of sustainable value creation are underway (WEF, 2020b). In any case, to be effective, the definitions of corporate responsibility and performance obtained from the concept of political CSR and the sustainable value-added metric must be embedded in the structures of companies. This is where business leaders have an essential role to play.

3.4.3 Leadership

Business leaders influence and often determine the mission and the vision of the company they manage (Finkelstein et al., 2009). Therefore, leaders have the power to determine how their company manages its social and environmental commitment (Mäkinen & Kourula, 2012; Matten & Moon, 2008). This position of control plays a central role in a company's decision to endorse a political responsibility (Borghesi et al., 2014). Maak et al. (2016) argues that responsible leaders who focus on business and societal objectives may incite their organizations to engage in political CSR and augment their firms' success to cope with the challenges of a globalized world. Therefore, an acute need exists for responsible leaders who can reform systems and prioritize investment to preserve the planet.

⁹ The Big Four refers to the four largest professional services networks in the world: Deloitte, E&Y, KPMG and PWC.

Business leaders have the opportunity to move beyond their legal obligations and uphold their responsibilities to society. In fact, the most powerful driver for business leaders to commit to climate change should be the conviction to contribute to changing the world. The second should be the preference to initiate the change rather than undergo it. Moreover, social and environmental commitment can attract a young and talented workforce, which in turns offers a long-term competitive advantage (Greening & Turban, 2000). Today's children striking for the climate gradually become tomorrow's adults, with working, voting and investing powers. Finally, companies' social and environmental commitment has a significant impact on employees' satisfaction and performance (Fu & Deshpande, 2013).

3.5 Conclusion on climate change

Stabilizing the climate requires urgent cuts in global GHG emissions, the protection and enhancement of biosphere carbon sinks, the removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere, and a global adaptation to the unavoidable damages of climate change (Steffen et al., 2018). These actions necessarily involve changes in governance, behavior, education, and consumption at a global level (Westley et al., 2011). At the same time, climate change globalizes and amplifies social inequalities. As a result, the nature of the challenge the world is facing is social before being economic. Therefore, a financial rationality will not allow a sustainable pathway to be reached.

Companies are major stakeholders in shaping the common future of the climate and have the power to be part of the solution to the global response to climate change. Business leaders embedded in an economic paradigm must realize that using the stock price as the main indicator of corporate performance is inappropriate in this situation. Companies can face the challenge of climate change only by maximizing economic, social and natural capital. This should be the definition of corporate performance. Therefore, companies must endorse political responsibilities to resolve issues of public goods. The implementation of the political CSR is a key element of this horizon since it defines the role companies must assume to respond to the climate crisis.

The battle regarding climate change promises to be extremely difficult. Any action taken may prove to be insufficient in the case of non-linear changes or once a tipping points is reached. Yet, climate change carries the message that each individual has its own part of responsibility

for the damages occurring around the world. In addition, climate change dissolves borders, cultures and inequalities in the face of a universal threat. This common enemy may be the best catalyst to forge a shared identity. Therefore, this climate crisis may also be a horizon of creativity and improvement for society.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper contributes to the discussion on the relation between climate commitment and corporate performance. The focus of this work is to emphasize major obstacles for companies to commit to climate change in the current economic models and to pave the way for a new definition of corporate responsibility and performance. This thesis also aims to gradually supplement the resources necessary for a more general awareness of the climate crisis since more thorough understanding can support the global response to this issue.

The objective of the first section of this paper is to prove that the use of financial metrics as primary indicators of corporate performance fails to account for the welfare of companies. The discussion is based on a systematic analysis of financial incentives for companies to engage in mitigation or adaptation measures from two distinct situations. The first situation is the motivation to commit on a voluntary and private basis. This paper comes to the conclusion that the incentives from previous studies, the benefits to mitigate GHG emissions and the advantages to adapt to climate change are strongly limited by business leaders' focus on immediate profit and short-term projects. The second situation is a study of climate-related risks that could force companies to commit to climate change. This paper explains that litigation, reputation and divestment risks are not sufficient incentives since they are limited by the general undervaluation of climate-related risks. Therefore, the first section highlights the necessity to change the definition of corporate performance and responsibility.

The second section of this paper analyses the general dynamics in a globalized world affected by climate change and observes that companies already endorse political responsibilities. This section explains that corporate performance must be defined by companies' capacity to maximize their economic, social and natural capital and emphasises that the concept of political CSR is the most appropriated solution for the global response to climate change. In addition, this section calls for further development of metrics to account for the companies' contribution to create or preserve public goods. The second part concludes on the need for responsible business leaders to prioritize investments in climate change.

Most research on climate change and corporate performance either focuses on the relation between environmental and financial performances or exclusively on the creation of alternative economic models. The originality of this thesis is found in its pathway to explain why it is

essential for the actual model to change given the actual state of climate change and what purpose companies should strive for. The main contribution of this paper is its observation that the economic paradigm in which business leaders are embedded is the biggest obstacle for the global response to climate change. Therefore, the findings and analysis of this thesis may raise interests among practitioners and academics on the discussion on how to cope with climate change.

The choice of working on a systematic analysis on the topic of climate change comes with its shortcomings. Climate economics is a rapidly developing field, with already a large body of academic papers. However, the author could not find any study explaining why the present economic systems are not appropriate given the climate crisis and how companies could orient themselves to respond to this issue. Therefore, the structure of this paper and the main conclusions are drawn from the author's own critical analysis and observations. Consequently, important climate-related risks or recent observations that could be solution or issues to the companies' response to climate change may have been omitted. In addition, since the author firmly believes in the seriousness of climate change, the views and opinions expressed in this paper are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect those of the general public. However, the author hopes that his analysis is logical and gives a useful reflection upon the obstacles and possible responses to the climate crisis.

REFERENCES

- ABI. (2004) A Changing Climate for Insurance – A Summary Report for Chief Executives and Policymakers. *Association of British Insurers, London, 20pp.*
- Ackerman, F., Stanton, E., & Hope, C. (2008). Climate change and the US economy: The costs of inaction. *The Center for Integrative Environmental Research.*
- Adger, W., Agrawala, S., & Mirza, M.M.Q. (2007). Assessment of adaptation practices, options, constraints and capacity. *Contribution of working group II to the fourth assessment report of the IPCC. 717-743.*
- Adler, D. (2018). U.S. Climate Change Litigation in the Age of Trump: Year One. Sabin Center for Climate Change Law. *Columbia Law School, Columbia Public Law Research Paper.*
- Agrawala, S., Carraro, M., & Kingsmill, N. (2011). Private Sector Engagement in Adaptation to Climate Change: Approaches to Managing Climate Risks. *OECD Environment Working Papers, No. 39.*
- Aktas, N., de Bodt, E., & Cousin, J. G. (2011). Do financial markets care about SRI? Evidence from mergers and acquisitions. *Journal of Banking & Finance, 35(7):1753– 1761.*
- Al-Najjar, B., & Anfimiadou, A. (2012). Environmental Policies and Firm Value. *Business Strategy and the Environment, 21(1), 49-59.*
- Alesina, A., & La Ferrara, E. (2000). Participation in heterogeneous communities. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics 115: 847-858.*
- Arbella Advisors. (2018). The Global Fossil Fuel Divestment and Clean Energy Investment Movement. *Arabella Advisors.*
- Ayling, J., & Gunningham, N. (2015). Non-State Governance and Climate Policy: The Fossil Fuel Divestment Movement. *SSRN Electronic Journal.*
- Badaracco, J.L. (1997). Defining Moments: When Managers Must Choose between Right and Right. *Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.*
- Bar-On, Y., Phillips, R., & Milo, R. (2018). The biomass distribution on Earth. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences. 115. 201711842.*
- Bardy, R. (2018). Public Goods, Sustainable Development and Business Accountability: Connecting Corporate Performance and Preservation of the Commons. *J Pol Sci Pub Aff 6: 339.*
- Bardy, R., & Massaro, M. (2015). Towards a Composite Index of Measuring Overall Corporate Performance: The Cost-of-Capital-Approach Expanded. *Corporate Governance. Vol 13, No.5.*

- Barney, J. (1991). Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- Baron, D.P. (2010). Morally motivated self-regulation. *American Economic Review*, 100, pp. 1299–1329.
- Barrage, L. (2020). Optimal Dynamic Carbon Taxes in a Climate–Economy Model with Distortionary Fiscal Policy. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 87(1).
- Bartomeus, I., Potts, S., & Steffan-Dewenter, I. (2014). Contribution of insect pollinators to crop yield and quality varies with agricultural intensification. *PeerJ*. 2. e328.
- Baumol, W. (1972). On Taxation and the Control of Externalities. *American Economic Review*, 62, issue 3, p. 307-22.
- Beck, U. (2000). *What Is Globalization?* Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bénabou, R. & Tirole, J. (2010). Individual and corporate social responsibility. *Economica*, 77, pp. 1–19.
- Bendell, J. (2018). Deep adaptation: a map for navigating climate tragedy. Institute for Leadership and Sustainability (IFLAS) *Occasional Papers Volume 2*. University of Cumbria, Ambleside, UK.
- Berlemann, M., & Steinhardt, M. (2017). Climate Change, Natural Disasters and Migration – A Survey of the Empirical Evidence. *CESifo Economic Studies*. 63. 353-385.
- Berrang-Ford, L., Biesbroek, R., & Ford, J. (2019). Tracking global climate change adaptation among governments. *Nature Climate Change*. 9. 440-449.
- Besley, T. & Ghatak, M. (2007). Retailing public goods: the economics of corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Public Economics*, 91, pp. 1045–1063.
- Beurden, P. & Gossling, T. (2008). The worth of values – a literature review on the relation between corporate social and financial performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 82. No. 2, pp. 69-82.
- Bhattacharya, C. B., Korschun, D., & Sen, S. (2009). Strengthening stakeholder–company relationships through mutually beneficial corporate social responsibility initiatives. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 85: 257–272.
- Biesbroek, R., Klostermann, J., Termeer, C., & Kabat, P. (2011). Barriers to climate change adaptation in the Netherlands. *Climate Law*, 2(2), 181-199.
- Boehmer-Christiansen, S. & Kellow, A. (2003). International environmental policy: interests and the failure of the Kyoto process. *Edward Elgar Publishing*.
- Borghesi, R., Houston, J. F., & Naranjo, A. (2014). Corporate socially responsible investments: CEO altruism, reputation, and shareholder interests. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 26, 164-181.

- Bouzzine, Y., & Lueg, R. (2020). The contagion effect of environmental violations: The case of Dieselgate in Germany. *Business Strategy and the Environment*.
- Boykoff, M., & Roberts, T. J. (2008). Media coverage of climate change: Current trends, strengths, weaknesses. *Human Development Report*.
- Bruch, S. & White, K. (2018). Politics, State discretion and retrenchment in safety net provision: evidence from the USA in the post-Welfare Reform era. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy, and Society*, 11: 459–483.
- Brysse, K., Reskes, N., & O'Reilly, J. (2013). Climate change prediction: Erring on the side of least drama? *Global Environmental Change, Volume 23, Issue 1*, pp.327-337.
- Bukit, R., Haryanto, B., & Ginting, P. (2018). Environmental performance, profitability, asset utilization, debt monitoring and firm value. IOP Conference Series: *Earth and Environmental Science*, 122(1), 6.
- Burchell, J., & Cook, J. (2006). Confronting the “corporate citizen”: Shaping the discourse of corporate social responsibility. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 26(3–4), 121–137.
- Cai, Y., Judd, K., & Lenton, T. (2015). Environmental tipping points significantly affect the cost–benefit assessment of climate policies. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. 112.
- Caldecott, B. & McDaniels, J. (2014). Financial dynamics of the environment: Risks, impacts, and barriers to resilience. *Working paper, The Stranded Asset Program*. SSEE, University of Oxford.
- Calzadilla, A. Zhu, T., & Rehdanza, T. (2013). Economywide impacts of climate change on agriculture in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Ecological Economics. Volume 93*, 150-165.
- Carney, M. (2015). Breaking the tragedy of the horizon - climate change and financial stability. Speech 29 September, Bank of England, Lloyds of London.
- Carnwath, J. (2016). Climate change adjudication after Paris: a reflection. *J. Environ. Law* 28(1): 5–9.
- Carroll, A. B. (1991). The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the Moral Management of Organizational Stakeholders. *Business Horizons*, 34, 39–48.
- Carroll, A. B., & Shabana, K. M. (2010). The Business Case for Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review of Concepts, Research and Practice. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 12(1), 85–105.
- Cawley, G. (2011). On the Atmospheric Residence Time of Anthropogenically Sourced Carbon Dioxide. *Energy & Fuels*. 25. 5503–5513.

- CDP. (2016). The business end of climate change. How bold corporate action supported by smart policy can keep temperature rise below 2°C. *We Mean Business and Carbon Disclosure Project*.
- CDP. (2017). The Carbon Majors Database. *CDP Carbon Majors Report 2017*.
- CDP. (2019). Major risk or rosy opportunity. Are companies ready for climate change? *CDP 2019*.
- Cetindamar, D. & Husoy, K. (2007). Corporate social responsibility practices and environmentally responsible behaviour: the case of the United Nations Global Compact. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 76, pp. 163–176.
- Challinor, A., Watson, J., & Lobell, D.B. (2014). A meta-analysis of crop yield under climate change and adaptation. *Nature Climate Change*. advance online publication.
- Cheal, A., Macneil, A., & Emslie, M. (2017). The threat to coral reefs from more intense cyclones under climate change. *Global Change Biology*. 23. 1511–1524.
- Chi-Shiun, L., Chih-Jen, C., Chin-Fang, Y. & Da-Chang, P. (2010). The effects of corporate social responsibility on brand performance; the mediating effect of industrial brand equity and corporate reputation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 95 No. 3, pp. 457-469.
- Clark, G. L. & Viehs, M. (2014). The implications of corporate social responsibility for investors: An overview and evaluation of the existing CSR literature. *SSRN working paper*.
- Cloutier, G., Joerin, F., & Dubois, C. (2014). Planning adaptation based on local actors' knowledge and participation: A climate governance experiment. *Climate Policy*. Advance online publication.
- Collins, M., & Knutti, J. (2013). Long-term Climate Change: Projections, Commitments and Irreversibility. In: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York.
- Cook J., Nuccitelli D., & Green S. A. (2013). Quantifying the consensus on anthropogenic global warming in the scientific literature. *Environmental Research letters* 8. 24024-7.
- Costanza, R. (2009). Toward a new sustainable economy. *Real-World Economics Review*, Vol. 49, pp. 20-21.
- Covington, H., & Thamotheram, R. (2014). How Should Investors Manage Climate-Change Risk? *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Crouch, C. (2009). Privatized Keynesianism: An Unacknowledged Policy Regime. *British Journal of Politics & International Relations*, 11(3).
- Dahlen, S. V. & Peter, G. V. (2012). Natural catastrophes and global reinsurance exploring the linkages. *BIS Quarterly Review*. 23–35.

- Dahlsrud, A. (2008). How Corporate Social Responsibility is Defined: An analysis of 37 Definitions. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 15, 1–13.
- Dangendorf, S., Marcos, M., & Woppelmann, G. (2017). Reassessment of 20th century global mean sea level rise. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 114.
- Davies, J., & Anthony S. (2018). Comparing global inequality of income and wealth. *WIDER Working Paper 2018/160*.
- Davis, M.A., Johnson, N.B., & Ohmer, D.G. (1998). Issue-Contingent Effects on Ethical Decision Making: A Cross-Cultural Comparison. *Journal of Business Ethics* 17, 373–389.
- De Bruin, K.C., Dellink, R.B. & Tol, R.S.J. (2009). AD-DICE: an implementation of adaptation in the DICE model. *Climatic Change* 95, 63–81.
- Déjean, F. (2005). L'Investissement Socialement Responsable – Etude du cas français [Socially Responsible Investment – A Study of the French Case] (Vuibert, Paris).
- Dirzo, R, Young, HS, & Galetti, M. (2014). Defaunation in the Anthropocene. *Science*, vol. 345, no. 6195, pp. 401-6.
- Dodd, J., & Chen, S. (1997) Economic Value Added (EVA). *Arkansas Business and Economic Review*. Vol. 30, N° 4.
- Dunning, J. (2009). Location and the multinational enterprise: John Dunning's thoughts on receiving the Journal of International Business Studies 2008 Decade Award. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 40(1), 20-34.
- Dyllick, T. & Hockerts, K.N. (2002), Beyond the business case for corporate sustainability. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Vol. 11 No. 2, pp. 130-141.
- EIA. (2019). International Energy Outlook 2019 with projections to 2050. *U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA)*. 2019.
- Elkington, J. (1999). Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century. *Business Capstone Publishing Ltd*, Oxford.
- Euzen, A., Laville, B., & Thiébault, S. (2017). Adapting to climate change. A question of Societies. CNRS editions, Paris, 2017.
- Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (1993). Common risk factors in the returns on stocks and bonds. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 33(1), 3–56.
- Fernandez-Feijoo, B., Romero, S., & Ruiz Blanco, S. (2014). Commitment to Corporate social responsibility measured through global reporting initiative reporting: Factors affecting the behavior of companies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 81. 244–254.
- Finkelstein, S., Hambrick, D. C. & Canella, A. (2009). Strategic leadership. *Oxford: Oxford University Press*.

- Fisher-Vanden, K., & Thorburn, K. S. (2011). Voluntary Corporate Environmental Initiatives and Shareholder Wealth. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 62 (3), 430-445.
- Fisher-Vanden, K., & Thorburn, K.S. (2008). Voluntary Corporate Environmental Initiatives and Shareholder Wealth. *Working Paper, Dartmouth College*.
- Flammer, C. (2013). Corporate Social Responsibility and Shareholder Reaction: The Environmental Awareness of Investors. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(3), 758– 781.
- Fracarolli Nunes, M., & Lee Park, C. (2016). Caught red-handed: the cost of the Volkswagen Dieselgate. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 7(2), 288-302.
- Frank W., Bals C., Grimm J. (2019). The Case of Huaraz: First Climate Lawsuit on Loss and Damage Against an Energy Company Before German Courts. (eds) *Loss and Damage from Climate Change. Climate Risk Management, Policy and Governance*. Springer, Cham.
- Friedlingstein, P., Jones, M., & O'Sullivan, M. (2019). Global Carbon Budget 2019. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 11, 1783–1838.
- Friedman, M. (1970). A Theoretical Framework for Monetary Analysis. *Journal of Political Economy*, 78(6), 193–238.
- Frieler, K., Meinshausen, M., & Golly, A. (2013). Limiting global warming to 2 °C is unlikely to save most coral reefs. *Nature Clim Change* 3, 165–170.
- Fu, W., Deshpande, S. (2013). The Impact of Caring Climate, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment on Job Performance of Employees in a China's Insurance Company. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 124. 339-349.
- Fullerton, D., & Kim, S. (2006). Environmental investment and policy with distortionary taxes, and endogenous growth. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*. 56. 141-154.
- Ganguly G, Setzer J, & Heyvaert V. (2018). If at first you don't succeed: suing corporations for climate change. *Oxf. J. Leg. Stud.* 38(4):841–68.
- GCA. (2019). Adapt now: a global call for leadership on climate resilience. *Global commission on adaptation*.
- Giddens A., (2009). The politics of Climate Change. *Polity Press*.
- Gjerde, K., Reeve, L., & Harden-Davies, H. (2016). Protecting Earth's last conservation frontier: scientific, management and legal priorities for MPAs beyond national boundaries. *Aquatic Conservation Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*. 26. 45-60.
- Goldenfeld, Nigel & Kadanoff, Leo. (1999). Simple Lessons from Complexity. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*. 284. 87-9.

- Goldstein, A., Turner, W.R., & Gladstone, J. (2019). The private sector's climate change risk and adaptation blind spots. *Nature Clim Change* 9, 18–25.
- Gomez, P., & Korine, H. (2005). Democracy and the Evolution of Corporate Governance. *Corporate Governance*, 13(6).
- Goodpaster, K. (1983). The concept of corporate responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics* 2, 1–22.
- Greening, D. W., & Turban, D. B. (2000). Corporate Social Performance as a Competitive Advantage in Attracting a Quality Workforce. *Business & Society*, 39(3), 254–280.
- Greenpeace. (2007). How the palm oil industry is cooking the climate. *Greenpeace*. 2007.
- Greenpeace. (2019). Amended petition. Requesting for Investigation of the Responsibility of the Carbon Majors for Human Rights Violations or Threats of Violations Resulting from the Impacts of Climate Change. *Greenpeace*.
- Greenwood, M. (2007). Stakeholder engagement: Beyond the myth of corporate responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 74(4), 315–327.
- Grimalda, G., & Tänzler, N. (2018) social cohesion, global governance and the future of politics. Understanding and fostering social cohesion. *T20 Argentina*.
- Grothmann, T. & Patt, A. (2005). Adaptive capacity and human cognition: the process of individual adaptation to climate change. *Global Environ. Chang.*, 15, 199-213.
- GSIR. (2018). Global sustainable investment review 2018. *Global Sustainable Investment Alliance*.
- Habermas, J (2001) The postnational constellation. *Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press*.
- Habermas, J. (1998). Between facts and norms. *Cambridge, MA: MIT Press*.
- Hallegatte, S., Green, C., & Nicholls, R. (2013). Future flood losses in major coastal cities. *Nature Climate Change*. 3. 802-806.
- Hansen, E., & Schaltegger, S. (2017). Sustainability Balanced Scorecards and their Architectures: Irrelevant or Misunderstood? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 150(4), 937-952.
- Harari Y.N., (2018). 21 Lessons for the 21st Century. *Spiegel & Grau, Jonathan Cape 2018*.
- Harrington LJ, & Otto F. (2019). Attributable damage liability in a non-linear climate. *Clim. Change* 153(1):15–20.
- Hart, S.L., & Ahuja, G. (1996). Does it pay to be green? An empirical examination of the relationship between emission reduction and firm performance. *Business Strategy and the Environment* 5 (1), 30–37.

- Harvey, F. (2019) One Climate Crisis Disaster Happening Every Week, UN Warns. *The Guardian*. 07 July 2019.
- Hess, D. (2007). Social reporting and new governance regulation: The prospects of achieving corporate accountability through transparency. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 17: 453–76.
- Hillman, A., Keim, G., & Schuler, D. (2004). Corporate Political Activity: A Review and Research Agenda. *Journal of Management*, 30(6), 837-857.
- Hjort, I. (2016). Potential climate risks in financial markets: A literature overview, *Memorandum, No. 01/2016*. University of Oslo, Department of Economics, Oslo.
- Hoffman, A., & Woody, J. (2008). Climate Change: What's Your Business Strategy?
- Hsieh, N. (2004). The obligations of transnational corporations: Rawlsian justice and the duty of assistance. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 14: 643-661.
- Hsu, A. W.-h. & Wang, T. (2013). Does the market value corporate response to climate change? *Omega*, 41(2):195–206.
- Hughes L. (2019). The Rocky Hill decision: A watershed for climate change action? *J. Energy Nat. Resour. Law* 37(3): 341–51.
- Hulme, M. (2010). Cosmopolitan Climates. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 27(2-3), 267-276.
- IEA. (2019), Global Energy & CO2 Status Report 2019. *IEA*, Paris.
- IPBES. (2019). Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. *IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany*.
- IPCC (2014): Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. *Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*.
- IPCC. (2007). Mitigation of Climate Change. *Contribution of Working Group III to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press: Cambridge.
- IPCC. (2013). Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. *Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*.
- IPCC. (2018). Summary for Policymakers. In: Global Warming of 1.5°C. *An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways*.
- Isaksson, R., & Steimle, U. (2009). What does GRI-reporting tell us about corporate sustainability? *The TQM Journal*, 21(2), 168-181.

- Jacobs, B., Singhal, V., & Subramanian, R. (2010). An Empirical Investigation of Environmental Performance and the Market Value of the Firm. *Journal of Operations Management*, 28, 430-441.
- Jaworek M., & Kuzel M. (2015). Transnational Corporations in the World Economy: Formation, Development and Present Position. *Copernican Journal of Finance & Accounting*, 4(1), 55–70.
- Jensen, M. C. (2002). Value Maximization, Stakeholder Theory, and the Corporate Objective Function. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 12(2), 235–256.
- Joos, F., Roth, R., & Fuglestedt, J. (2013). Carbon dioxide and climate impulse response functions for the computation of greenhouse gas metrics: a multi-model analysis. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 13.
- Keeling, C. D. (1960). The concentration and isotopic abundances of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. *Tellus*, 12(2), 200–203.
- Keenan, T., Prentice, I., & Canadell, J. (2016). Recent pause in the growth rate of atmospheric CO₂ due to enhanced terrestrial carbon uptake. *Nat Commun* 7, 13428.
- Khan, M., & Roberts, J. (2013). Adaptation and international climate policy. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: *Climate Change*, 4.
- Kjellstrom, T., Maître N., & Saget, C. (2019). Working on a warmer planet. The impact of heat stress on labor productivity and decent work. *International Working Labor*.
- Klassen, R. D. & McLaughlin, C. P. (1996). The Impact of Environmental Management on Firm Performance. *Management Science*, 42(8):1199–1214.
- Köhler, P., Hauck, J., & Voelker, C. (2017). Comment on Scrutinizing the carbon cycle and CO₂ residence time in the atmosphere. *Global and Planetary Change*, 164.
- Kolk, A. & Pinkse, J. (2005). Business responses to climate change: identifying emergent strategies, *California Management Review*, 47(3), pp. 6–20.
- Kolk, A. & Pinkse, J. (2007). Towards strategic stakeholder management? Integrating perspectives on sustainability challenges such as corporate responses to climate change. *Corporate Governance*, Vol. 7 No. 4, pp. 370-378.
- Kuhlman, T., & Farrington, J. (2010). What is Sustainability? *Sustainability*, 2(11), 3436–3448.
- Lakonishok, J., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1994). Contrarian Investment Extrapolation and Risk. *The Journal of Finance*, 49(5), 1541–1578.
- Lambeck, K., Purcell, A., & Zhao, J. (2010). The Scandinavian Ice Sheet: From MIS 4 to the end of the Last Glacial Maximum. *Boreas*, 39, 410 - 435.
- Lancee, B., & Van de Werfhorst, H. (2011). Income inequality and participation: a comparison of 24 European countries. *GINI discussion paper; No. 6*. Amsterdam: AIAS.

- Lear, J. (2009). *Radical Hope: Ethics in the Face of Cultural Devastation*. *Bibliovault OAI Repository*. the University of Chicago Press.
- Leijten I. (2019). Human rights v. insufficient climate action: the Urgenda case. *Neth. Q. Hum. Rights* 37(2):112–18.
- Lenton, T., Rockström, J., & Gaffney, O. (2019). Climate tipping points — too risky to bet against. *Nature*, vol 575, 592-595.
- Levy N. (2019). Juliana and the political generativity of climate litigation. *Harvard Environ. Law Rev.* 43(2):479–506.
- Lobao, L., Adua L., & Hooks, G. (2014). Privatization, business attraction, and social services across the United States: local governments' use of market- oriented, neoliberal policies in the post-2000 period, *Social Problems*, 61: 1–27.
- Lopez-Santana, M. (2015). *The New Governance of Welfare States in the United States and Europe*. *Albany, New York: The State University of New York Press*.
- Lord, N., Ridgwell, A., & Thorne, M. (2015). An impulse response function for the 'long tail' of excess atmospheric CO₂ in an Earth system model. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*. 30.
- Lorenzoni, I. & Pidgeon, N. (2006). Public views on climate change: European and USA perspectives. *Climatic Change*, 77, 73-95.
- Lovejoy, T. & Nobre, C. (2018). Amazon Tipping Point. *Science Advances*. Vol 4, no. 2.
- Maak, T., Pless, N., & Voegtlin, C. (2016). Business Statesman or Shareholder Advocate? CEO Responsible Leadership Styles and the Micro-Foundations of Political CSR. *Journal of Management Studies*. 53.
- Mackey, A., Mackey, T. B., & Barney, J. B. (2007). Corporate social responsibility and firm performance: Investor preferences and corporate strategies. *Academy of Management Review*, 32(3), 817–835.
- Mäkinen, J. & Kourula, A. (2012). Pluralism in political corporate social responsibility. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 22, 649-78.
- Malmquist, D. (2018). Researchers issue first-annual sea-level report cards. *Phys.org*, 12 March.
- Margolis, J. D., & Walsh, J. P. (2003). Misery Loves Companies: Rethinking Social Initiatives by Business. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 48(2), 268–305.
- Marshall M., (2020, May 26). Planting trees doesn't always help with climate change. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20200521-planting-trees-doesnt-always-help-with-climate-change>
- Matten, D. & Crane, A. (2005). Corporate citizenship: toward an extended theoretical conceptualization. *Academy of Management Review*, 30, pp. 166–179.

- Matten, D. & Moon, J. (2008). "Implicit" and "explicit" CSR: A conceptual framework for a comparative understanding of corporate social responsibility. *Academy of Management Review*, 33, 404-24.
- McGlade, C., & Ekins, P. (2015). The geographical distribution of fossil fuel unused when limiting global warming to 2°C. *Nature*, 517, p187-190.
- McGuire, S. (2013). Multinational and NGOs amid a changing balance of power. *International Affairs*, 89, pp. 695– 710.
- McKillop, A. (2010). Oil and the Deepwater Frontier. *Energy & Environment*, 21(7), 841-845.
- Mengel, M. & Levermann, A. (2014). Ice plug prevents irreversible discharge from East Antarctica. *Nature Climate Change*. 4. 451-455.
- Mercure, J., Pollitt, H., & Viñuales, J.E. (2018). Macroeconomic impact of stranded fossil fuel assets. *Nature Clim Change* 8, 588–593.
- Moser, S. (2005). Impacts assessments and policy responses to sea-level rise in three U.S. states: an exploration of human dimension uncertainties. *Global Environ. Chang.*, 15, 353-369.
- Nakao, Y., Amano, A., Matsumura, K., Genba, K., & Nakano, M. (2007). Relationship between environmental performance and financial performance: An empirical analysis of Japanese corporations. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 16(2):106–118.
- Naqvi, S. (2013). Impact of Corporate Social responsibility on Brand image in Different FMCGs of Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary journal of contemporary research in business*.
- NOAA. (2019). National Centers for Environmental Information, State of the Climate: Global Climate Report for Annual 2019.
- OECD. (2019). Climate finance provided and mobilized by developed countries. 2013-17, *OECD Publishing, Paris*.
- OECD. (2019). Under Pressure: The Squeezed Middle Class. *OECD Publishing, Paris*.
- Oliver, J., Janssens-Maenhout, G., & Muntean, M. (2014). Trends in Global CO2 Emissions: 2013 Report. *PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency*.
- Orlitzky, M. (2013). Corporate Social Responsibility, Noise, and Stock Market Volatility. *The Academy of Management Perspectives*, 27(3), 238–254.
- Overland, J., Dunlea, E., & Box, J. (2019). The urgency of Arctic change. *Polar Science*, 6-13.
- Owen, D. (2008). Chronicles of wasted time? A personal reflection on the current state of, and future prospects for, social and environmental accounting research. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 21(2), 240-267.

- Park, B.J.R., Srivastava, M.K. & Gnyawali, D.R. (2014). Walking the tight rope of competition: impact of competition and cooperation intensities and balance on firm innovation performance. *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol. 43, No. 2, pp.210–221.
- Pecl, G., Araújo, M., & Bell, J. (2017). Biodiversity redistribution under climate change: Impacts on ecosystems and human well-being. *Science*. 355.
- Peel J, Osofsky H, & Foerster A. (2017). Shaping the “next generation” of climate change litigation in Australia. *Melb. Univ. Law Rev.* 41(2):793–844.
- Peel, J., & Osofsky, H. (2020). Climate Change Litigation. *Annual Review of Law and Social Science*. 16.
- Peñuelas, J., Ciais, P., & Canadell, J.G. (2017). Shifting from a fertilization-dominated to a warming-dominated period. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*.
- Perrow, Charles. (2000). An Organizational Analysis of Organizational Theory. Contemporary Sociology-a Journal of Reviews - *CONTEMP SOCIOLOG.* 29. 469-476.
- Pfrommer T, Goeschl T, & Proelss A. (2019). Establishing causation in climate litigation: admissibility and reliability. *Clim. Change* 152(1): 67–84.
- Piaget, J. (2005). The future of developmental child psychology. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 3(2), 87-93.
- Pithan, F., & Mauritsen, T. (2014). Arctic amplification dominated by temperature feedbacks in contemporary climate models. *Nature Geoscience*. 7.
- Polonsky, M.J., Miles, M.P. & Grau, S.L. (2011). Climate change regulation: implications for business executives. *European Business Review*, Vol. 23 No. 4, pp. 368-383.
- Prahalad, C., & Hammond, A. (2002). Serving the world's poor, profitably. *Harvard business review*, 80(9), 48, 124-57, 124.
- Radeloff, V., Helmers, D., & Kramer, H. (2018). Rapid growth of the US wildland-urban interface raises wildfire risk. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 115(13): 3314-3319.
- Rahmstorf, S., & Coumou, D. (2011). Increase of extreme events in a warming world. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(44), 17905.
- Ramiah, V., Martin, B., & Moosa, I. (2013). How does the stock market react to the announcement of green policies? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 37(5):1747–1758.
- Rasche, A., & Kell, G. (2010). The UN Global Compact: Achievements, trends and challenges. *Cambridge/New York: Cambridge University Press*.
- Robiou du Pont, Y., & Meinshausen, M. (2018). Warming assessment of the bottom-up Paris Agreement emissions pledges. *Nature Communications*. 9.

- Rogers., Blanchard, J., & Mumby, P. (2017). Fisheries productivity under progressive coral reef degradation. *Journal of Applied Ecology*.
- Rosen, B., Sandler, D., & Shani, D. (1991). Social Issues and Socially Responsible Investment Behavior: A Preliminary Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 25(2).
- Ruzzenenti, F., Font Vivanco, D., & Galvin, R. (2019). Editorial: The Rebound Effect and the Jevons' Paradox: Beyond the Conventional Wisdom. *Frontiers in Energy Research*. 7. 90.
- Sánchez-Bayo, F., & Wyckhuys, K. (2019). Worldwide decline of the entomofauna: A review of its drivers. *Biological Conservation*. 232.
- Sasse-Werhahn, L. (2019). The Practical Wisdom behind the GRI. *Humanistic Management Journal*, 4(1), 71-84.
- SBTi. (2019). Exploring the Science Based Targets initiative's progress in driving ambitious climate action. *Science Based Targets*.
- Scherer, A., & Palazzo, G. (2011). The New Political Role of Business in a Globalized World: A Review of a New Perspective on CSR and its Implications for the Firm, Governance, and Democracy. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(4).
- Scherer, A.G. (2018). Theory Assessment and Agenda Setting in Political CSR: A Critical Theory Perspective. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 20(2), 387-410.
- Scherer, A.G. & Palazzo, G. (2007). Toward a political conception of corporate responsibility: business and society seen from a Habermasian perspective. *Academy of Management Review*, 32, pp. 1096–1120.
- Scherer, A.G. & Palazzo, G. (2011). The new political role of business in a globalized world: a review of a new perspective on CSR and its implications for the firm, governance and democracy. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48, pp. 899–931.
- Scherer, A.G., Palazzo, G. & Matten, D. (2014). The business firm as a political actor: a new theory of the firm for a globalized world. *Business & Society*, 53, pp. 143–156.
- Scherer, A.G., Palazzo, G. & Seidl, D. (2013). Managing legitimacy in complex and heterogeneous environments: sustainable development in a globalized world. *Journal of Management Studies*, 50, pp. 259–284.
- Scherer, A.G., Rasche, A., Palazzo, G. & Spicer, A. (2016). Managing political corporate social responsibility: new challenges and directions for PCSR 2.0. *Journal of Management Studies*, 53, pp. 273–298.
- Schleussner, C., Pfleiderer, P., & Fischer, E. (2017). In the observational record half, a degree matter. *Nature Clim Change* 7, 460–462.
- Schmidt, J. (2000). Disciplined Minds - A Critical Look at Salaried Professionals and the Soul-Battering System that Shapes their Lives, *Rowman & Littlefield*, pp.293.

- Servaes, H., & Tamayo, A. (2013). The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Firm Value: The Role of Customer Awareness. *Management Science*, 59(5), 1045-1061.
- Setzer J, & Vanhala L.C. (2019). Climate change litigation: a review of research on courts and litigants in climate governance. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Clim. Change* 10(3): e580.
- Setzer, J., & Benjamin, L. (2020). Climate Litigation in the Global South: Constraints and Innovations. *Transnational Environmental Law*, 9(1), 77-101.
- Sherman, M. H., & Ford, J. (2014). Stakeholder engagement in adaptation interventions: An evaluation of projects in developing nations. *Climate Policy*, 14, 417–441.
- Snyder, B. & Jones, S. (2015). Here’s a timeline of Volkswagen’s tanking stock price. *Fortune*, 23 September.
- Sosdian, S., Greenop, R., & Hain, M. (2018). Constraining the evolution of Neogene ocean carbonate chemistry using the boron isotope pH proxy. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*. 498. 362-376.
- Spalding, M., Ruffo, S., & Lacambra, C. (2014). The role of ecosystems in coastal protection: Adapting to climate change and coastal hazards. *Ocean & Coastal Management*. 90. 50–57.
- Sprinkle, G.B. & Maines, L.A. (2010). The benefits and costs of corporate social responsibility. *Business Horizons*, Vol. 53 No. 5, pp. 445-453.
- Steffen, W., Rockström, J., Richardson, K. (2018). Trajectories of the Earth System in the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(33), 8252-8259.
- Stern, N. (2006). Stern review: the economics of climate change. United Kingdom.
- Stokes, B., Wike, R., & Carle, J. (2015). Global concern about climate change, broad support for limiting emissions. *Pew Research Center*.
- Sundaram, A., & Inkpen, A. (2004). The Corporate Objective Revisited. *Organization Science*, 15(3), 350-363.
- Sussman, F., & Freed, R. (2008). Adapting to climate change: A business approach. *Pew Center on Global Climate Change*.
- Telle, K. (2006). It pays to be green: A premature conclusion? *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 35(3):195–220.
- Thomas, J.A., Telfer, M.G., & Roy, D.B. (2004). Comparative losses of British butterflies, birds, and plants and the global extinction crisis. *Science* 303, 1879–1881.
- Tol, R. (2005). Adaptation and mitigation: Trade-offs in substance and methods. *Environmental Science & Policy*. 8. 572-578.

- UN. (1987). Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development Our Common Future. *NGO Committee on Education of the Conference of NGOs from United Nation*.
- UN. (2011). Guiding Principles on Business and Human rights. *United Nations*.
- UN. (2019). United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. *World Population Prospects 2019: Highlights*.
- UNCG. (2011). Adapting for a Green Economy: Companies, communities and climate change. A caring for climate report. *UN Global Compact, UN Environment Programme, Oxfam and the World Resources Institute*.
- UNEP. (2012). Business and Climate Change adaptation: toward resilient companies and communities. *UN Global Compact and UN environment programme*.
- UNEP. (2019). Emissions Gap Report 2019. *United Nations Environment Programme, Nairobi*.
- UNFCCC. (2015). Paris Agreement to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. *Dec. 12, 2015, T.I.A.S. No. 16-1104*.
- UNFCCC. (2015). Paris Agreement to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. *Dec. 12, 2015, T.I.A.S. No. 16-1104*.
- Uslaner, M., & Brown, M. (2005). Inequality, trust, and civic engagement. *American Politics Research* 33: 868-894.
- Van Aalst, M. (2006). The impacts of climate change on the risk of natural disasters. *Disasters*, 30(1).
- Verisk Maplecroft, (2013, October 30). 31% of global economic output forecast to face climate change risks by 2025. <https://www.maplecroft.com/insights/analysis/global-economic-output-forecast-faces-high-or-extreme-climate-change-risks-by-2025/>
- Villavicencio Calzadilla P. (2019). Climate change litigation: a powerful strategy for enhancing climate change communication. *ed. W Leal Fihlo, B Lackner, H McGhie*, pp. 231–46.
- Vogel, D. (2008). Private global business regulation. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 11, pp. 261–282.
- Waddock, S. (2016). Foundational Memes for a New Narrative About the Role of Business in Society. *Humanistic Management Journal*, 1(1), 91-105.
- Wadhams (2016) *A Farewell to Ice*, Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Wadhams, P. (2018). Saving the world with carbon dioxide removal. *Washington Post*, 8 January.
- Wagner, M. & Wehrmeyer, W. (2002). The relationship of environmental and economic performance at the firm level: A review of empirical studies in Europe and methodological comments. *European Environment*, 12(3):149–159.

- Walsh, K., Camargo, S., & Knutson, T.R. (2019). Tropical cyclones and climate change. *Tropical Cyclone Research and Review*, 8. 240-250.
- Wang, Q., Dou, J., & Jia, S. (2016). A meta-analytic review of corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance: The moderating effect of contextual factors. *Business & Society*, 55(8): 1083–1121.
- Warren, R., Price, J., & Graham, E. (2018). The projected effect on insects, vertebrates, and plants of limiting global warming to 1.5°C rather than 2°C. *Science*, 360. 791-795.
- Watkins, S. (2003). Ethical Conflicts at Enron: Moral Responsibility in Corporate Capitalism. *California Management Review*, 45(4), 6-19.
- Watson, R., McCarthy, J., & Canziani, P. (2019). The Truth Behind the Climate Pledges. 10.13140/RG.2.2.23744.28169.
- Wedawatta, G., & Ingirige, B. (2012). Resilience and adaptation of small and medium-sized enterprises to flood risk. *Disaster Prevention and Management*, 21(4), 474-488.
- WEF. (2019). Regional Risks for Doing Business 2019. In partnership with Marsh & McLennan Companies and Zurich Insurance Group. Insight Report.
- WEF. (2020). The Global Risks Report 2020. In partnership with Marsh & McLennan and Zurich Insurance Group. *Insight Report*, 15th Edition.
- WEF. (2020b). Toward Common Metrics and Consistent Reporting of Sustainable Value Creation. Prepared in collaboration with Deloitte, EY, KPMG and PwC. Consultation Draft.
- Werther, W., & Chandler, D. (2005). Strategic corporate social responsibility as global brand insurance. *Business Horizons*, 48. 317-324.
- Westley, F., Olsson, P., Folke, C. (2011) Tipping toward sustainability: Emerging pathways of transformation. *Ambio* 40: 762–780.
- Whalley, M. (2016). Legal risk 2.0: Show you're in control. *Ernst and Young*. 2016
- Wiebe, K., Lotze-Campen, H., & Sands, R. (2015). Climate change impacts on agriculture in 2050 under a range of plausible socioeconomic and emissions scenarios. *Environmental Research Letters*, Volume 10, Number 8.
- Wood, G. & Wright, M. (2015). Corporations and the new statism: trends and research priorities. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 29, pp. 271–286.
- Yamaguchi, K. (2008). Reexamination of stock price reaction to environmental performance: A GARCH application. *Ecological Economics*, 68(1-2):345–352.
- Zhang, P., Zhang, J., & Chen, M. (2016). Economic impacts of climate change on agriculture: The importance of additional climatic variables other than temperature and precipitation. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, Volume 83, pp.8-31.

Zito, A.R. (2005). The European Union as an environmental leader in a global environment. *Globalizations*, 2 (3), 363–375.

Web pages

<https://www.wemeanbusinesscoalition.org/companies/> (Description of initiatives and firms committed). Last checked on the 24th of August 2020.

<https://sciencebasedtargets.org/companies-taking-action/> (More information on companies' commitments). Last checked on the 24th of August 2020.

<https://www.globaljustice.org.uk/news/2018/oct/17/69-richest-100-entities-planet-are-corporations-not-governments-figures-show> (List of the 100 largest economic entities). Last checked on the 24th of August 2020.